

D3.1 Algorithms Definition, Baselines, Open Issues and Use Cases

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Abstract	This report presents Deliverable D3.1, offering and methodological exploration of knowledge representation, with a focus on enhancing context-aware dialogue systems through contextual information. It outlines the algorithms for handling of contextual elements within dialogue systems acting in low-risk and high-risk scenarios, focusing on improve interpretability and trustworthiness, aligning with ELOQUENCE's objectives of developing hybrid LLMs for effective conversational agents.		

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ATS	Automatic Text Summarization
BLEU	Bilingual Evaluation Understudy
COT	Chain-of-Thought
DC	Direct Compute
DJC	Direct Joint Compute
D2F	Dialog-To-Flow
E2E	End-to-End
IR	Information Retrieval
KR	Key result
LLM	Large Language Model
MT	Machine Translation
NER	Named Entity Recognition
PTC	Predict-then-Compute
RAG	Retrieval Augmented Generation
ROUGE	Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation
STAR	Schema-guided Dialog Dataset for Transfer Learning
TOD	Task Oriented Dialog
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This report constitutes the first deliverable (D3.1) of Work Package 3 (WP3) and presents the outcomes of in-depth discussions on the formalization and representation of knowledge, with a particular focus on the role of contextual information in shaping explainable and effective context-aware interactions within unstructured dialogues. It explores the theoretical and methodological foundations for defining 'knowledge' and delineates strategies for determining what contextual factors to incorporate, how to model them, and at which stages of the interaction pipeline they are most impactful.

Deliverable D3.1 summarizes the ongoing research and experimental work carried out under Work Package 3 (WP3), with a particular focus on **Task T3.1** (Interpretable and Trustworthy AI-Based Systems for Low-Risk Scenarios) and **Task T3.3** (Self-Supervised Learning for Effective Context-Aware Dialogue Systems). Both tasks share a common goal: enhancing the performance and interpretability of dialogue systems through the accurate encoding of contextual information. Task T3.1, initiated in Month 12 (M12), focuses on low-risk scenarios—such as smart home assistants handling simple information requests. It explores techniques for incorporating shallow and semi-deep contextual knowledge to support transparency and user trust (detailed in Chapter 4). In contrast, Task T3.3, which began in Month 16 (M16), targets high-risk and constraint-sensitive applications. It investigates the integration of complex contextual signals—such as multi-turn dependencies and multilingual inputs—into dialogue systems designed for critical settings (discussed in Chapter 5). Given the varying stages of maturity across these tasks, the primary aim of this deliverable is to provide a broad conceptual and methodological overview that lays the groundwork for the subsequent implementation phases within the next stages of the ELOQUENCE project.

Overall, T3.1 and T3.3 support ELOQUENCE objectives 2 (KR5, K6, KR7) and 3 (KR8, KR9), which aim to: (i) develop hybrid LLMs capable of processing speech and/or text inputs while leveraging contextual knowledge to improve explainability in semi-structured and unstructured dialogues; and (ii) enhance conversational agents to promote unbiased and trustworthy interactions with end-users.

2 Introduction

The field of conversational artificial intelligence (AI) has witnessed significant advancements, especially with the rise of Large Language Models (LLMs) (Bubeck, et al., 2024; Lu, et al., 2022; Hendrycks, et al., 2021; Hendrycks, et al., 2020; Cobbe, et al., 2021). Conversational AI has moved beyond simple rule-based systems towards more sophisticated agents capable of engaging in nuanced and informative dialogues. A key focus in this evolution is the development of agents that are both context-aware and knowledge-based. Context-aware conversational AI aims to understand and leverage the dynamic history and specifics of a conversation, including user intent, prior turns, to generate relevant and coherent responses (Naik, Metallinou, & Goel, 2018; Melo, Alencar, & Cowan, 2025). This capability is crucial for creating interactions that feel natural and personalized, moving beyond generic replies to address the specific needs and ongoing context of the user.

In addition to context awareness is the integration of knowledge bases, which aims to equip conversational agents with structured information that can be accessed and utilized during a dialogue (Ngai, Lee, Luo, Chan, & Liang, 2021; Caffaro & Rizzo., 2024). By grounding their responses in factual, in-domain data and semantic relationships, knowledge-based agents can provide more accurate, informative, and insightful answers compared to models relying solely on patterns learned from dialogue corpora (Callejas-Rodríguez, Villatoro-Tello, Meza, & Ramírez-de-la-Rosa, 2016). The synergy between understanding the conversational context and accessing relevant knowledge is thus paramount for building truly intelligent conversational agents that can effectively assist end users.

Furthermore, as context-aware and knowledge-based conversational AI agents become integrated into increasingly sensitive and high-risk domains such as healthcare, finance, and legal assistance, the aspect of explainability gains significant importance. Understanding *why* an agent provides a particular response, especially when dealing with critical or personal information, is crucial for building user trust and ensuring accountability (Wölfel, 2024). In scenarios where decisions or recommendations are being made based on the dialogue, the ability to trace back the reasoning to the specific contextual elements and knowledge sources not only enhances transparency but also allows for verification and potential correction of errors.

Accordingly, and in line with ELOQUENCE's main goal—research and development of conversational dialogue systems—WP3 activities focus on developing innovative solutions for building context-aware conversational AI agents capable of maintaining coherent, fluent, and meaningful communication with users. A key objective of WP3 is to foster explainability and coherence in the system's generated responses, enabling both human-in-the-loop and end-users to understand how the model's decisions are being made.

Thus, this report describes the current defined methodologies, baselines and preliminary results in the context of the WP3 planned activities and how these are connected to the high-level ELOQUENCE research goals. **Chapter 3** outlines the conceptual foundations and design choices related to the definition and representation of *context* and *domain knowledge* within conversational AI systems. It provides a framework for how these elements will be operationalized across the tasks to be developed in the project. **Chapter 4** presents the research conducted on dialogue system applications in low-risk scenarios, such as smart home assistants. Specifically, it explores how text summarization techniques can serve as a tool for enhancing interpretability in dialogue systems (Section 4.1). It also discusses efforts to analyze and interpret the underlying semantics of embedding spaces used in language models (Section 4.2), as well as preliminary work on extracting fine-grained, interpretable cues to support retrieval-based response generation (Section 4.3). **Chapter 5** details the activities focused on developing LLM-based dialogue systems for high-risk scenarios. In particular, Section 5.1 introduces the Dialog2Flow model—a framework for learning dialogue actions and latent semantics in task-oriented conversations—which serves to enhance the interpretability of sentence embeddings within conversational contexts. Section 5.2 further examines the role of context integration in LLM-based dialogue systems, using the NurseLLM pilot as a case study. This pilot is designed to assist medical staff by guiding conversations with parents reporting health concerns about their newborns, emphasizing safety, factual consistency, and explainability. Finally, **Chapter 6** offers preliminary conclusions and discusses the next steps for WP3.

2.1 Relation to other WPs

As previously mentioned, the primary goal of WP3 is to research, develop, evaluate, and integrate advanced AI techniques for context-aware conversational dialogue systems capable of maintaining coherent, fluent, and meaningful interactions with users. The resulting technology will enable the implementation of new strategies to enhance the explainability and coherence of system-generated responses. This will allow both human-in-the-loop participants and end-users to understand the rationale behind the model's decisions and outputs.

Accordingly, WP3's activities are directly interconnected with the following tasks across other work packages (WPs):

- **WP1 – T1.4:** Integrated Metrics for Multi-Functional Systems Supporting Multilinguality, Multimodality, Efficiency, and Rapid Adaptation for Bias-Controlled and Privacy-Aware Models. The evaluation metrics developed in WP1 will be employed to assess conversational LLMs within WP3. A key objective is to measure the extent to which AI-driven conversational agents adhere to predefined policies and dialogue flows while minimizing hallucinations and maintaining factual correctness.
- **WP2 – T2.1:** Adapting LLMs to Complex Conversational Data. WP3 will contribute to the development of language models capable of capturing not only the semantic content of a conversation but also the underlying user intentions and dialogue acts. This goes beyond mere surface-level text understanding, enabling richer and more contextually appropriate responses.
- **WP2 – T2.3:** Dialog goal identification and tracking. WP3 will investigate and evaluate different approaches for the integration of multilingual summarization strategies to improve long-term context-awareness and response generation in multi-turn dialogues.
- **WP4 – T4.2:** Leveraging multimodality for context-aware multilingual speech models. WP3 will explore and evaluate various approaches to incorporate and encode contextual information in both low- and high-risk scenarios. This work complements ongoing efforts in T4.2, where emotion recognition and dialogue history (i.e., previous turns) are being investigated to enhance the performance of multimodal and multilingual ASR systems.
- **WP4 – T4.3:** Architectures and Training Protocols for Privacy-Aware and Data-Efficient Speech Modeling. WP3 will leverage the expertise and findings from T4.3 and, in turn, contribute efficient alternatives for designing, training, and deploying End-to-End ASR architectures connected to LLMs, with a focus on data efficiency.
- **WP5 - Pilot 1:** Privacy-preserving language model learning through decentralized training in smart homes. Developments related to federated learning summarization and context-awareness through generated multi-turn conversation summaries will support the use case in smart assistants in Pilot 1, maintaining consistent memory of pertinent contextual information and relating responses to inputs through attention methods and context-specific knowledge. **Pilot 4:** Upgrading support call centers through AI-based Supervision of multimodal dialogues. Developments within WP3 are particularly relevant to the use case defined in Pilot 4, where an AI-based assistant is designed to support medical staff in providing advice to new parents reporting health-related issues concerning their newborns, referred as the *NurseLLM*. WP3 will contribute solutions aimed at enhancing the assistant's behavior by ensuring that the system consistently tracks relevant contextual information and constrains its responses to factual and explainable outputs through the integration of domain-specific knowledge.

2.2 Expected Outcomes

Concretely, the main expected outcomes are:

1. The integration of human knowledge, either domain-specific or open domain, with recent deep learning techniques in a scalable exploration-exploitation strategy for explainable decision-making in the context of dialogue systems.
2. Improving context-aware human-machine interaction by enhancing dialogue encoding, adding to the dialogue system the capacity to produce coherent answers from partially observed data.

3. Developing models that will be particularly useful for data-limited but complex, evolving problems in specific and open domains (high-risk and low-risk scenarios), improving explainability and enabling trustworthy AI-based solutions.

3 Towards Building Reliable LLM-based Dialogue Systems: Boosting Interpretability Through Context, and Domain Knowledge

The advent of LLMs has fundamentally reshaped the landscape of artificial intelligence, propelling conversational agents from niche applications to widespread adoption across diverse domains. These powerful models, trained on vast corpora of text, demonstrate an unprecedented ability to generate human-like language, engage in nuanced dialogue, and even perform complex reasoning tasks. Consequently, LLM-based systems are rapidly becoming the cornerstone of next-generation dialogue interfaces, promising more intuitive, efficient, and natural interactions between humans and machines.

ELOQUENCE WP3's main goal is to support the development of reliable LLM-based dialogue systems. Generally speaking, reliability, in this context, transcends mere fluency; it encompasses trustworthiness, predictability, and the ability to consistently deliver accurate and appropriate responses. Achieving this level of reliability necessitates a deep dive into three interconnected pillars: interpretability, context management, and the effective integration of domain knowledge.

This chapter explores the foundational requirements for building reliable LLM-based dialogue systems, emphasizing that reliability is not solely a matter of generative fluency. It argues that such systems must exhibit interpretable behavior, maintain a coherent and context-aware understanding of the ongoing dialogue, and adhere to clearly defined interaction policies. In addition, their responses should be grounded in verifiable external knowledge, ensuring that outputs can be traced, validated, and trusted in both design and deployment contexts.

3.1 Human Knowledge Integration for Task Oriented Dialogues

It is well known that a long-standing challenge in computer science is to develop algorithms that can interact with human users via dialogue in natural language. One case is task-oriented dialogues (TOD), wherein a user interacts with an AI-based agent to achieve a particular goal (e.g., making a doctor appointment). The agent should understand the user's queries and assist them by taking the appropriate actions, e.g., searching in a database for availability, and making entries to such a database. Although recent research has shown the potential of supervised approaches for learning complex patterns from conversational data (in open-domain dialogues) without requiring any specific hand-crafted rules, it is unclear how effectively transfer skills to tasks and domains that were not present during the training of such models, i.e., how to transfer this learnt knowledge to TOD scenarios.

The STAR (Schema-Guided Dialog Dataset for Transfer Learning) dataset (Mosig, 2020) is a significant resource in the field of conversational AI, specifically designed to address the challenge of creating dialogue systems that can adapt to new tasks and domains with minimal or no additional training data (zero-shot transfer learning).

Unlike open-domain dialogues, TODs are accompanied by a set of steps that are necessary to complete the task. These steps are typically known a priori (i.e., *domain knowledge*) and thus do not have to be learned from the data. For practical applications, it is desirable that we could make modifications to this logic (*domain knowledge*) without having to discard large parts of the dataset. The ideal sequence of steps that a dialogue would follow to complete the task can be arranged in a graph (see for example in Figure). Together with the utterances or actions that are associated with the nodes of the graph, the authors of the STAR dataset refer to this as a *task schema*, i.e., the "expert's knowledge" about how a task should be structured and how a conversational agent should ideally behave.

A key characteristic of the STAR dataset is that each task is explicitly defined by a schema. This schema acts as a blueprint for the dialogue, outlining the valid intents (user goals), slots (pieces of information needed to fulfil the goal), and potential actions the system can take. The dataset explicitly records the knowledge base queries made by the system, providing a clear link between the dialogue state and the information retrieved to respond to the user.

In essence, STAR leverages human knowledge at multiple levels: from the initial, abstract definition of a task and its conversational flow in a schema, to the realistic and adaptive human-human interactions during data collection, and finally to the detailed annotation that grounds the natural language to the structured task representation. This incorporation of human expertise is what enables STAR to be such a powerful and attractive dataset for developing

generalizable task-oriented dialogue systems within the context of the ELOQUENCE project. Although START is an English-language dataset, working with it will help validate the impact of incorporating human knowledge into LLM-based dialogue systems. The insights and expertise gained can later be applied and validated in a multilingual setup, which is the primary objective of WP4 in the ELOQUENCE project.

Figure 3-1: Flow chart representation for the schema-graph for the book_doctor_appointment task.

3.1.1 Relation of task-schemas within WP3 main goals

LLM-based dialogue systems are conversational AI systems that leverage the capabilities of LLMs to engage in human-like conversations. Unlike traditional rule-based or statistical dialogue systems that often rely on predefined rules or extensive data for specific tasks, LLM-based systems can generate more flexible, natural, and diverse responses. Nevertheless, current LLM-based dialogue systems are unpredictable due to hallucinations and misaligned behavior and hard to control due to their black-box nature. Consequently, such systems are generally not trustable and their adoption in real-world commercial applications is limited, especially in high-risk or task-oriented scenarios.

Integrating task schemas—or modeling dialogues as trajectories within a conversational latent space that can be merged and pruned to reveal the underlying dialogue flow—has the potential to significantly improve LLM-based dialogue systems. This approach can enhance both controllability and interpretability by grounding the system in domain-specific dialogue structures.

Concretely, one line of research that will be explored within WP3 involves assessing the impact of infusing domain knowledge (either as task-schema or as dialog flows) in the following tasks:

1. **Script adherence scores:** As of today, there is no standard metric(s) to quantify hallucinations and misaligned behavior of conversational dialogues beyond simple word-based metrics such as perplexity, ROUGE or BLEU. We aim to explore how to take advantage of dialogue flows/task-schemas to design evaluation metrics that go beyond word-based towards flow-based metrics that also consider the expected conversational steps within dialogues.
2. **Dialogue flow-grounded LLMs:** Recently, a significant effort has been made to help LLMs better support the contextualization and abstraction within a conversation, resulting in a richer language model encoding

in the embedding space. We aim to explore how to take advantage of dialogue flows to ground LLMs-based dialogue systems to improve their controllability and interpretability.

Initial work done in this direction is further explained in Section 5.1, where we describe our proposed methodology to design conversation models in the form of finite state graphs semi- or fully automatically from an unlabeled set of audio and textual task-oriented dialogues. Our proposed solution, referred to as Dialog2Flow is capable of modeling conversations as trajectories in a conversational latent space that can be merged and pruned to extract the underlying dialogue flow.

3.2 Understanding Context for Coherent Dialogues

In dialogue systems, *context* encompasses all information necessary for understanding and generating appropriate responses across a conversation. It forms the shared common ground—both explicit (e.g., previous utterances, named entities) and implicit (e.g., speaker intent, conversational goals)—that enables coherent and effective communication. Unlike single-turn question-answering systems, dialogue involves multiple interdependent turns, where the interpretation of a current utterance is often shaped by prior exchanges, user-specific information, and external situational factors. Capturing and leveraging this context is critical for building systems that can maintain continuity, relevance, and responsiveness throughout the interaction.

Open-domain dialogue systems have demonstrated impressive conversational capabilities (Adiwardana, et al., 2020; Roller, et al., 2021), yet their limited domain grounding and imprecise context management restrict their use in sensitive, high-stakes scenarios. In such environments—like healthcare, legal, or safety-critical operations—systems must emphasize accuracy, interpretability, and strict adherence to operational constraints to ensure user safety and trustworthiness. To address these challenges, this section presents a framework for enhancing context awareness in TOD systems by leveraging both static and dynamic context components, creating stable yet adaptive conversational agents.

3.2.1 Static and Dynamic Context

A robust dialogue system requires careful differentiation and integration of **static context** and **dynamic context**. Static context encompasses persistent directives—such as the system’s role, high-level goals, and strict safety guardrails—that remain invariant throughout the interaction. These directives serve as foundational constraints, ensuring the system’s behavior remains aligned with predefined operational boundaries.

Dynamic context evolves in real time during the conversation and includes the interaction history, recognized entities, and relevant external knowledge sources. This dynamic information allows the system to maintain situational awareness, adapt to user input variations, and generate contextually appropriate responses.

3.2.1.1 Static Context: Role Specification, Safety Guardrails, and Context Tracking

- **Role and Goal Specification** involves explicitly defining the system’s identity and interaction objectives via system prompts or configuration settings. For example, framing the system as an information-elicitation agent restricts dialogue content and style to relevant, goal-directed exchanges, minimizing off-topic or casual dialogue. This framing shapes the system’s response generation, aligning it with task-specific requirements.
- **Safety and Relevance Guardrails** implement hard operational limits to prevent undesirable behaviors, such as providing advice outside the system’s expertise or engaging in irrelevant queries. These guardrails are encoded as explicit constraints in system instructions and monitored continuously to avoid safety breaches and maintain conversation efficiency.
- **Context Tracking Instructions** detail how the system should handle multi-turn memory and information flow, a critical capability for maintaining coherence and relevance over the dialogue. Four key sub-skills are central here:
 - **Context Retention:** Maintaining a coherent memory of past dialogue turns and facts, enabling seamless references and preserving interaction continuity (Tomar, 2024).
 - **Contextual Inference:** Utilizing accumulated context to proactively determine relevant next actions or questions, moving beyond isolated turn-based understanding (Xing, Yin, Yan, & Wang, 2021).

- **Handling Implicit Information:** Extracting unstated or implied user information to enrich internal representations, crucial for thorough understanding (Xing, Yin, Yan, & Wang, 2021; Zhang & Song, 2024).
- **Resolving Contextual Inconsistencies:** Detecting contradictions or ambiguous information and prompting clarifications to maintain trustworthiness and accuracy (Zhang, Jin, Song, Mi, & Yu, 2024).

Overall, this layered static context framework ensures the system operates with well-defined roles, safety constraints, and sophisticated memory management, collectively supporting coherent and reliable dialogue performance.

3.2.1.2 *Dynamic Context: Dialogue History, Named Entities and External Knowledge Integration*

- **Dialogue History** (Adiwardana, et al., 2020; Shi, et al., 2024) refers to the sequence of all previous utterances in the conversation, forming the temporal backbone for coherence and relevance in multi-turn dialogue models. Effective retention and utilization of dialogue history prevent disjointed responses and allow the system to build progressively on shared knowledge.
- **Named Entity Recognition (NER)** plays a vital role in structuring domain-specific information within the dialogue. Extracting key entities—such as symptoms, times, or relevant concepts—enhances semantic understanding and enables grounding in external knowledge bases (Xing, Yin, Yan, & Wang, 2021). Advanced dialogue systems incorporate entity embeddings to improve comprehension and response precision (Varshney, Zafar, Behera, & Ekbal, 2023; Qu, Li, Ma, & Li, 2023).
- **External Knowledge Sources** further enrich dynamic context by incorporating retrieved domain-relevant data, such as curated question-answer pairs or real-world dialogue examples (Gatto, et al., 2025). Retrieval-augmented generation approaches combine the generative power of LLMs with evidence-based context, reducing hallucinations and supporting naturalistic yet clinically appropriate follow-ups (Upadhyay & Viviani, 2025; Li, i drugi, 2018).

Together, these dynamic context elements enable dialogue systems to adaptively respond to evolving conversational states while maintaining grounding in both immediate interaction history and broader domain knowledge.

As part of WP3 activities, we will explore the impact of integrating these two context types, to develop LLM-based dialogues systems with a balance of stability and safety from static constraints with flexibility and awareness from dynamic updates, crucial for sensitive applications. Preliminary experiments and results are further described in Section 0.

4 Approaching Low-Risk Dialogue Applications: Methodology and Preliminary Results

This chapter presents a suite of exploratory methodologies and preliminary findings aimed at improving dialogue quality, transparency, and contextual relevance in low-risk domains. We investigate how different interpretability-focused techniques can be used both as evaluation instruments and as components of the dialogue system itself.

We first explore the utility of text summarization techniques to condense interaction history and generate interpretable intermediate representations, which help both human users and systems reason over long exchanges (Section 4.1). We then analyze how sentence embeddings can serve as a lens into a model's latent semantic processing, offering interpretable cues about conversational relevance and progression (Section 4.2). We then shift to fine-grained interpretability by adapting Information Retrieval (IR) methods to extract token-level relevance cues. These signals offer localized explanations for why certain system responses or user inputs are contextually prioritized (Section 4.3). Finally, we introduce CopyLM, a novel span-copying mechanism designed to address inefficiencies in autoregressive generation. By enabling the model to copy previously generated sequences in a single step, CopyLM improves both response coherence and inference efficiency—particularly valuable in dialogue where repetition is common (Section 4.4).

Together, these contributions demonstrate how interpretability methods can be repurposed from evaluation tools into integral system components. They provide empirical foundations for building scalable, transparent dialogue systems, in line with ELOQUENCE's broader goals of fostering accountability and trust in AI-mediated communication

4.1 *Text Summarization for Interpretability and Long-term Dialog Improving*

Automatic Text Summarization (ATS) allows managing voluminous data more effectively and facilitates informed decision-making. For example, governmental institutions summarize extensive policy documents and reports, aiding policymakers in strategy formation and goal prioritization. Similarly, social media entities employ summarization to oversee current events, enabling journalists to rapidly compose articles on emerging topics. An explanation is an attempt at extracting useful, concise information from a complex, black-box model. Likewise, a summary attempts to extract the essential bits of a longer piece of text. Seen this way, an explanation summarizes the model's prediction, and a summary explains the summarized piece of text. It is thus beneficial to consider the two problems together since approaches to one can inform the approaches to the other.

4.1.1 Motivation

Summarization technology facilitates the creation of short, condensed versions of long and complex documents, thereby permitting users to concentrate on the most significant content. This leads to better comprehension and retention of the most critical information, saving time to review more material in less time allowing to make better informed decisions.

The relationship between explainability and ATS is dualistic, meaning they may mutually contribute to and benefit each other (Kasneci., 2024). This interaction is particularly critical given that deep learning models used for ATS are often "black boxes" that do not provide immediate insight into their internal workings. This opacity can lead to incorrect outputs that appear legitimate, creating an "illusion of understanding," making explainability vital for building trust and transparency, especially in sensitive applications like law and healthcare.

For example, some recent works (Kasneci., 2024; Vakharia, 2024) report that better summarization abilities can help overcome hallucinations, making LLMs more reliable and easier to interpret. They also focus on detecting and labeling hallucinations, that is, inaccuracies or fabrications in summaries, which directly supports interpretability by clarifying which parts of the output are faithful to the source. Summarization aids in the detection of hallucinations and inconsistencies, which are major obstacles to trusting LLM outputs. By making it easier to spot when a model has strayed from the source material, summarization supports both interpretability and explicability (Han, 2024).

Additionally, summarization is a foundational technique for infusing and maintaining knowledge in multi-turn conversations (Qingyue, 2025). Summarization models can process and condense large volumes of conversational data quickly, thus enhancing scalability and making them suitable for real-time applications such as customer support or multi-speaker dialogues. Summarization in multi-turn conversations is a powerful technique for infusing and retaining knowledge throughout prolonged, helping to keep context-rich dialogues. This approach addresses challenges such as context window limitations, information recall, and the integration of external knowledge, ultimately enhancing both the coherence and informativeness of conversational AI systems (Saha, 2024).

This section delves into the application of ATS within the ELOQUENCE project and its capacity to (1) improve interpretability and (2) enrich prolonged conversational interactions, exploring the utilization of summarization methodologies to augment the efficacy of the model's conversational capabilities.

4.1.2 Abstractive Text Summarization

When discussing automatic text summarization, an important distinction is made between extractive and abstractive summarization:

Extractive summarization: *Extracts exact words and phrases from the text itself to create a summary.*

Abstractive summarization: *The key information of the original text is maintained using semantically consistent words and phrases.*

Abstractive summarization more closely resembles the way humans write summaries and due to its complexity, it relies on advances in Deep Learning techniques like LLMs to be successful. For those reasons we are more interested in the application of abstractive summarization.

Figure 4-1: Averaged attention weights represented in shaded yellow, lighter shade indicating a higher level of importance.

Figure 4-1 shows an example of abstractive summarization using data from the UNS pilot, shaded in green at the bottom of the conversation. In this example, the abstractive summarization approach not simply extracts large proportions of the incoming text, but creates a human-like summary being:

"The caller is concerned about their 13-month-old baby who has had a fever for two days, with the highest temperature reaching 38.5°C. The baby also has increased night awakenings, is breastfeeding more frequently, and has nasal congestion. The nurse advises using a nasal aspirator with saline solution to clear the baby's airways and recommends consulting a visiting nurse.

Through the application of contextually coherent vocabulary and expressions, the summary distills the essence of the initial text into a concise and short form that facilitates quick comprehension, such as when a medical doctor needs to grasp the key points of a conversation rapidly during a subsequent consultation. This distillation helps stakeholders comprehend and retain critical information, which is foundational for interpretability. In such way, users can more easily understand what information the model considers most relevant (Pan, 2022).

4.1.3 Attention-based method for interpretability

One of the most straightforward and widely adopted method for elucidating a model's decision-making process and internal mechanisms is through the visualization of attention weights. Although it is a misconception to equate attention directly with explanations, this technique can still yield plausible and meaningful insights into model behavior (Zuidema., 2020). This transparency facilitates a quick audit trail of the model's decisions, making it more straightforward to comprehend which specific elements were considered or excluded, by clarifying which parts of the output are faithful to the source. This directly bolsters the model's interpretability by highlighting the sections of the output that accurately reflect the source content.

The attention mechanism within a model's transformer architecture can be viewed as a category of local explanation techniques for the outcomes of LLMs. Attention in this context signifies the method by which transformer models identify significant associations among all elements within the input sequence, determining which tokens are most crucial for establishing the output. This capability allows the model to comprehend the syntactic and semantic interrelations among words within a sentence, thus enabling it to produce an appropriate response. The relationship for each pair is given an attention score, a numerical value where higher means that the relationship between these two words is very important to the overall meaning of the sentence.

In Transformer-based models, self-attention is a mechanism that allows each token in the input sequence to attend to other tokens (Jesse, 2019). This is crucial for capturing dependencies regardless of their distance in the sequence. In decoding, a Transformer applies multi-head cross-attention at each layer. The cross-attention mechanism assigns to each input token x_i a set of attention weights over the tokens of the output sequence x_j :

$$Attn(x_j) = (\alpha_{1j}(x), \alpha_{2j}(x), \dots, \alpha_{ij}(x))$$

Here, $\alpha_{ij}(x)$ represents the attention that token x_j pays to token x_i . In causal models (right-to-left), $\alpha_{ij}(x)$ is defined only for $j \leq i$. The attention weights $\alpha_{ij}(x)$ are computed using the scaled dot-product of the query vector of x_i and the key vector of x_j , followed by a softmax operation:

$$Attn(Q, K, V) = softmax\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V$$

Where Q, K and V are the query, key, and value matrices respectively, and d_k is the dimension of the key vectors. In a multi-layer, multi-head setting, each head in each layer computes its own set of attention weights. This allows the model to capture different types of relationships between tokens. To visualize attention across the model with respect to the generated sequence, we can average the attention weights $\alpha_{ij}(x)$ across all heads and layers at each token generation. This results in a single attention matrix A where each entry A_{ij} represents the average attention from token x_i to x_j :

$$A_{ij} = \frac{1}{L \cdot H} \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{h=1}^H \alpha_{ij}^{(l,h)}$$

Here, L is the number of layers, H is the number of heads per layer, and $\alpha_{ij}^{(l,h)}$ is the attention from x_i input token to x_j output token in layer l and head h .

To visualize these underlying attention "scores" one could apply this concept to tasks like summarization. It helps to illustrate the practical use of attention mechanisms as a form of localized explanatory tool in the context of an LLM summary task. Given a phone call conversation, we want our model to produce an abstractive summary. The

example uses the Mistral-Nemo-Instruct-24071 LLM model that is instruct fine-tuned version of Mistral-Nemo-Base-2407. At the bottom of the Figure, a part of the summary is shaded in blue:

“13-month-old baby who has had a fever for two days, with the highest temperature reaching 38.5°C.”

Shaded in yellow, it exposes the attention weights of the LLM input sequence with respect to the blue part of the summary. The saturation of yellow background within the conversation is directly proportional to the attention scores obtained as the averaging across layers and attention heads. It is clear to see that this can help users in “seeing” how the LLM model captures relationships in the process of figuring out how to produce a specific part of the summary. If we look along the yellow words, we can see that some words are given more attention with respect to the shaded blue part of the summary, which can be seen as lighter shades of yellow. Here, some key words that meet this description are “thirteen months” and “fever”. The model tends to associate important relationships between the input conversation and the blue shaded part of the summary by attending several parts together, for example “thirteen months”, “thirty-eight point three” and “five”.

The attention mechanism within transformer-based models enables a quick analysis of the connections between each pair of input-output sequences. The visualization of these scores offers stakeholders a window into the rationale behind the LLM's summarization choices. Nevertheless, interpreting these visualizations can sometimes prove challenging. This underscores the notion that although attention visualization is a valuable tool for model interpretation, it should ideally be used alongside additional methods to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of the model's decision-making processes.

4.1.4 Federated Learning for Cross-lingual Summarization

We are currently conducting a series of experiments to investigate the potential of Federated Learning (FL) for multilingual abstractive summarization. As described in Deliverable 2.1 or Deliverable 5.1, FL is a decentralized learning paradigm in which multiple clients collaboratively train a shared model without sharing their raw data. Instead, only model updates, such as weights, are shared during each communication round. In this study, we focus specifically on multilingual scenarios, where each client operates in a different language, simulating realistic cross-lingual and privacy-preserving training environments.

This research is guided by the following key questions. First, we investigate the suitability of federated learning for multilingual training in the task of summarization and how it compares to traditional centralized (on-site) approaches. Second, we examine whether multilingual FL can enhance client-side performance compared to centralized multilingual methods. We aim to identify which languages benefit most from cross-lingual knowledge transfer within a federated setting. This analysis provides insights into the transferability of multilingual knowledge in FL settings. Third, we explore strategies for dynamically selecting or excluding clients that exhibit performance saturation during communication rounds, based on their validation and test results evaluated on server-side data.

To address these research questions, we have designed a series of fine-tuning experiments involving the following configurations: (a) multilingual on-site LLM, (b) multilingual FedLLM, (c) monolingual on-site LLM, (d) monolingual FedLLM, and (e) monolingual on-site LLM using the data proportion of a single client. Figure 4-2 illustrates these different experimental scenarios in the case of having 4 clients. These experiments are intended to establish strong baselines and upper/lower bounds, enabling us to compare the performance of centralized versus federated multilingual training (i.e., a vs. b) and to evaluate how individual clients benefit from multilingual exposure (a, b vs. e).

For our fine-tuning experiments, we utilize the XL-Sum dataset (Tahmid, et al., 2021) —a large-scale, professionally curated collection comprising 1.35 million article-summary pairs sourced from the BBC. XL-Sum is highly abstractive, concise, and of consistently high quality, as confirmed by both human and intrinsic evaluations. It spans 45 languages, ranging from low- to high-resource, making it particularly well-suited for multilingual research. For our

¹ <https://huggingface.co/mistralai/Mistral-Nemo-Instruct-2407>

purposes, we focus on a subset of European languages: English, Spanish, Portuguese, French, Russian, Serbian (Cyrillic), and Serbian (Latin). We selected XL-Sum primarily for its multilingual nature.

Figure 4-2: Experimental scenarios for 4 clients.

While other summarization-oriented datasets such as SAMSum (Gliwa, Mochol, Biesek, & Wawer, 2019) and DialogSUM (Chen, Yang, Chen, & Zhang, 2021) are also noteworthy, they are monolingual and therefore less aligned with the multilingual emphasis of our current work. Nevertheless, their focus on dialogue and chat-oriented data makes them highly relevant to the broader goals of the Eloquence project. SAMSum consists of 16,000 messenger-style conversations with summaries, created by English-speaking linguists to reflect real-life messaging behavior. DialogSUM includes 13,460 dialogues, each paired with manually annotated summaries and topic labels, offering a complementary perspective on dialogue summarization. These datasets may be explored in future experiments, particularly to study the impact of data heterogeneity in federated learning environments.

For our experiments, we employ the instructed Salamandra 2B multilingual model, which has not been pre-trained on the XL-Sum dataset. This allows us to evaluate the model’s adaptability to new summarization tasks under FL conditions.

To support these experiments, we extended the FederatedScope-LLM framework (Kuang, et al., 2024) with several key enhancements tailored to multilingual FL. First, we implemented functionality to ensure comparable experimental conditions, where each client in the FL setup receives an equal number of training samples. Second, we introduced a flexible prompt management system that allows the integration of task-specific prompts and avoid just using the default ones. For instance, we hand-crafted and incorporated the following prompt for the task of summarization:

Summarize the following text into one concise sentence that captures its main idea.

Text:
[Text to summarize]
Summary:

Given the multilingual nature of our setup, prompts must be language-specific and dynamically adapted to the language of each sample. To accommodate this, we enabled prompt variation at the sample level, ensuring that the correct language-specific prompt is applied. See below examples of the same prompt for Spanish, Portuguese and French used in our experiments.

Resume el siguiente texto en una sola oración concisa que capture su idea principal.

Texto:
[Text to summarize]
Resumen:

Resuma o texto seguinte numa única frase concisa que capte a sua ideia principal.

Texto:
[Text to summarize]
Resumo:

Résumez le texte suivant en une seule phrase concise qui capture l'idée principale.

Texte:
 [Text to summarize]
 ### Résumé:

Additionally, we implemented token-length-based filtering and developed a robust dataset partitioning mechanism to prepare the data for multilingual FL scenarios. This process includes generating validation and test sets for the central server, as well as training, validation, and test sets for each individual client, while maintaining consistent data proportions across both clients and languages. This ensures fair and balanced training and evaluation in a multilingual federated setting.

Figure 4-3 presents a visual example of a multilingual FL dataset configuration involving four clients (i.e., distinct languages), illustrating the corresponding data partitions assigned to the server and each client.

Figure 4-3: Example of dataset partitioning in multilingual FL for 4 clients.

So far, we have designed two multilingual FL configurations. The first setup includes four clients—Spanish, English, Portuguese, and French—while the second expands to seven clients by adding Russian, Serbian (Cyrillic) and Serbian (Latin). To ensure uniformity, we filtered all training, validation and test samples so that the combined prompt and input text does not exceed 3000 tokens. For the 4-client configuration, we selected 10,500 samples per language, resulting in a total of 42,000 samples. In the 7-client setup, we selected 8,300 samples per language, totaling 58,100 samples. Table 4-1 presents the number of samples allocated to each dataset split across the two multilingual FL configurations.

Table 4-1: Number of samples for each dataset split in the multilingual FL settings

# clients	Server		Clients		
	Val	Test	Train	Val	Test
4	500	500	9120	190	190
7	500	500	7008	146	146

4.1.4.1 Evaluation Metrics

In order to ensure comparability, forthcoming investigations into this task will employ identical metrics for evaluation as those previously utilized in Deliverable 2.3, particularly within Section 6.2.1.3.: **BLEU Score** (Pap02), **METEOR Score** (Banerjee & Lavie, 2005), **ROUGE Score** and **BERT Score** (Tianyi, Varsha, Felix, Kilian, & Yoav, 2019). **BLEU Score** (Papineni, Roukos, Ward, & Zhu, 2002), **METEOR Score** (Banerjee & Lavie, 2005), **ROUGE Score** (Lin, 2004) and **BERT Score** (Tianyi, Varsha, Felix, Kilian, & Yoav, 2019).

4.1.5 Future Directions

Conversational AI systems are intended to facilitate meaningful dialogue between humans and machines using natural language. Assistants within these systems are expected to deliver precise, relevant, and context-aligned responses, which in turn cultivate trust between the user and the AI. To achieve this, researchers have designed data-driven dialogue systems with a particular focus on modeling multi-turn conversations. In such systems, a classical approach is to use previous utterances as input to generate contextual responses. For instance, (Lowe,

2015) combined all previous utterances and the last utterance to form a context representation and (Yan, 2016) selected previous utterances using different strategies and combined them with the last utterance to create a reformulated context.

Summarization can be used to play a crucial role in enhancing context retention and engagement during multi-turn conversations. For instance, approaches like recursive summarization (Wang, et al., 2025) have proven effective in infusing context-awareness into multi-turn conversations, thereby improving conversational AI systems' ability to provide coherent, informative, and contextually relevant interactions. This method not only enriches the conversation but also ensures better user experiences, more effective knowledge exchange by improving context inference. Advanced models, such as MMK-Summation (Saha, 2024), integrate external knowledge and multi-modal information during the summarization process. In the work by (Wang, et al., 2024) dialogue summarization is used to enhance response generation by using a summarization model that employs the query and the generated summarization from the previous turns. This results in summaries that are not only concise but also contextually enriched with relevant background information. The generated dialogue summarization is fed to the response decoder as dialogue states and key dialogue histories through a fusion mechanism to yield responses.

As a future direction, we propose to incorporate generated summaries into long multi-turn interactions. For example included as an enhanced prompt (Wang, et al., 2025), to further optimize the conversational process and contextual memory for long conversations, see Section 3.2.1.2. Generated summaries of ongoing dialogues become instrumental in extracting essential elements and preserving topic flow and context retention, facilitating easier recollection of crucial details and tracking the progression of discussions. This strategy seeks to complement the research initiated in Task 2.3 that focus on dialogue managers, as delineated in Section 6.2 of D2.3. By enhancing the response generator through using efficient context-knowledge infusion (Xing, Yin, Yan, & Wang, 2021), our objective is to overcome limitations such as finite context window in LLMs and information recall. This will be explored through a process of recursive summarization that systematically prunes out irrelevant parts of the dialog and ultimately enhancing both the coherence and informativeness. This is particularly useful in lengthy or diverging conversations wherein context can easily be lost and wherein LLMs, and even bigger models such as GPT-4, tend to struggle when trying to recall information from previous interactions despite of incorporating large context windows. Figure 4-4 depicts an example of how a recursive summarization strategy can be incorporated as part of the response generator.

Figure 4-4: Proposed iterative summarization method for continuous infusion of context

4.2 Sentence embeddings interpretation

Recent years have seen numerous successful approaches to building joint speech-text representation models. The abundance of textual data compounded by paired speech-text and unpaired / unlabeled speech data, powered by self-supervised and contrastive learning methods enabled such models to learn robust representations. Applications requiring understanding of the language (grammar, semantics) greatly benefit from joint

representation learning. Despite being difficult to compress all the semantic information present in a sentence into a single vector, they are convenient and useful for several applications such as sentence classification and retrieval.

Here, we will provide a brief overview of the SONAR model (Duquenne, Schwenk, & Sagot, 2023), its training scheme, and its applications. Note that there exist several models, with SONAR being one of the latest ones covering numerous written (200) and spoken (37) languages. SONAR is trained in a two-step process as shown in Figure 4-5. The first step is to learn a shared sentence embedding space across multiple languages but using only textual data. In the second step, the speech utterance embeddings are extracted to be mapped to the textual sentence embedding space using the knowledge distillation approach. The textual module in SONAR is an encoder-decoder transformer architecture initialized from NLLB (no language left behind), a massive multilingual machine translation (MT) model that covers 200 languages. The speech encoder is initialized from wav2vec-2.0-bert², a model based on self-supervised learning.

Figure 4-5: Architecture of SONAR

4.2.1 Interpreting semantics of sentence embeddings

We introduce a proxy task for extracting the most representative keywords (n -grams) from sentence embeddings by linear projection onto the word embedding matrix. We train a log-linear model that explains the bag-of-words present in the text sentence given the embedding of the utterance (text, speech).

Consider a data set of N sentence pairs of speech and text. Let $\{(\mathbf{t}_1, \mathbf{s}_1), \dots, (\mathbf{t}_n, \mathbf{s}_n), \dots, (\mathbf{t}_N, \mathbf{s}_N)\}$ represent N pairs of sentence embeddings of textual and spoken utterances respectively, extracted from a joint representation model such as SONAR. Each sentence embedding is a single vector of fixed dimension, that is $\mathbf{t}_n, \mathbf{s}_n \in \mathbb{R}^d$.

Let V denote a set of words in vocabulary extracted from the corpus of N textual sentences, and \mathbf{x}_n represent the vector of count statistics of words present in the sentence n .

Let $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{|V| \times d}$ represent the embeddings for each unique word from the vocabulary V , and $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^{|V| \times 1}$ represent the bias vector. The log-linear model is trained to maximise the regularised log-likelihood of the data (bag-of-words) as follows:

$$\theta_n = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{b} + \mathbf{W} \mathbf{t}_n)$$

$$\phi_n = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{b} + \mathbf{W} \mathbf{s}_n)$$

² <https://huggingface.co/facebook/w2v-bert-2.0>

$$\arg \max_{W, b} \sum_n \alpha \log \theta_n^T x_n + (1 - \alpha) \log \phi_n^T x_n - R(W)$$

Here $R(W)$ is the (L_2) regularization term for the word embeddings, and α is the weight balancing the log likelihood of the data with respect to textual or spoken sentence embeddings.

4.2.1.1 Extracting keywords

Once the model is trained, the most representative words are extracted using a single linear projection of the sentence embedding onto the embedding matrix W . The bias vector b is ignored as it acts as a background model and mainly carries the weight for the most frequent terms (stop words).

$$\eta = W t$$

where $\eta \in \mathbb{R}^{|V|}$ represents the scores (logits) that indicate the relevance of each word to the sentence embedding. Note that, in the original vocabulary V there will be synonyms or words with different verb forms that have higher score. To pick top k distinct words from the scores, we follow a simple heuristic based on word-embedding similarity that avoids semantically closer words. An example of the output shown below in Table 5-1 where the first row is the reference text, and the words below are the extracted from speech embedding using our log-linear model as described earlier. Words with high cosine similarity are put in the same column in descending order of the logit (Ardila, et al., 2020) score. The cosine similarity threshold is tuned on the development set and is typically in the range (0.6, 0.8). We can see that the model is able to identify semantically similar word embeddings.

4.2.2 Experiments

Initial experiments for baseline systems were conducted on Mozilla Common Voice corpus (Ardila, et al., 2020). We picked English, and French speech and text as part of our initial experiments. We used the standard training splits from the corpus to estimate the parameters and used the dev set for hyper-parameter tuning and test set for evaluation. Table 4-2 shows basic statistics of the employed dataset.

Table 4-2 Mozilla Common-Voice Dataset Statistics

Language	Tarin hours	Dev hours	Test hours	Total hours
English	~2.2K hrs	~30 hrs	~31 hrs	~2.3K hrs
French	~634 hrs	~20 hrs	~20 hrs	~674 hrs

4.2.2.1 Evaluation

We compute precision and recall by comparing the extracted keywords against the ground truth reference. This tells how many unigrams extracted by taking top- k from the logits (linear projection of sentence embedding on weight embedding matrix) are present in the test transcript. An example is shown below in Table 4-3, where first row is the reference text, and the words below are the extracted ones. Words with high cosine similarity are put in the same column, with the first one having a higher logit score. By considering the top 5 words (bold ones), we will have a precision of 1.0, and a recall of 0.5. Note that these keywords are extracted directly from speech embedding.

Table 4-3: Example illustrating top- k retrieved keywords from a speech embedding.

She began writing at the young age of thirteen years old				
thirteen	age	writing	began	she
thirteenth	old	-	started	-
fourteen	years	-	-	-

sixteen	young	-	-	-
fifteen	aged	-	-	-

4.2.2.2 Results

The results are presented by computing precision and recall as a function of top k extracted keywords, where $k = 1, 2 \dots 20$. The keywords are extracted independently from textual and speech embeddings. The Figure 4-6 shows the results for English test from Mozilla common voice. The PR curves for both text and speech overlap (hence not clearly distinguishable) indicating that both speech and text embeddings are very close and are able to yield the keywords that have same precision and recall. We can also see that the precision for top 5 is almost 0.78 indicating that richness of the embedding extract from SONAR and also the capability of the log-linear model.

Figure 4-7 represents the same PR curve but for French test set from Mozilla common voice. Here we can see that the PR curves for text and speech do not overlap as they did for English, indicating that the representations are slightly different, nevertheless very close. We can also see that Precision at top 5 is about 0.55, which is much lower as compared to English, indicating that embeddings extracted for French samples are not as semantically rich as the ones extracted for English samples.

Figure 4-6: Precision and recall for English test set

Figure 4-7: Precision and recall for French test set

4.2.3 Summary and future directions

To advance ELOQUENCE’s goal of building transparent and multilingual dialogue systems, we plan to conduct experiments across a wide range of languages and datasets, leveraging diverse embedding models such as LaBSE and BGE. These experiments will help us identify the limitations of current multilingual sentence encoders in capturing semantically rich and consistent representations across both textual and spoken modalities. By evaluating the informativeness of extracted keywords—using both human judgments and LLM-based annotations as reference—we aim to assess how well model-derived representations align with human-interpretable cues. Our use of a log-linear model as a comparative baseline enables systematic analysis of whether these extracted elements reflect human-preferred relevance patterns, a core requirement for building dialogue systems that are not only accurate but also explainable and trustworthy, in line with ELOQUENCE’s overarching research agenda.

4.3 Interpretable Fine-grained Relevance Cues from Information Retrieval

4.3.1 Motivation and Initial Results

The motivation behind the need for fine-grained information retrieval is its importance in enhancing the performance of various NLP tasks. For example, highlighting what is relevant in the text leads to noticeable speed-up of query-document judgement without the drop in accuracy (Leonhardt et al., 2023), faster question answering (Feng & Boyd-Graber, 2019).

First, we conducted preliminary experiments on retrieving the most relevant parts of the text using post-hoc explainability methods. These techniques are typically applied to neural models, but for a retrieval task, we incorporated them into a reranking setup, using a retrieve-and-rerank pipeline. Post-hoc interpretability methods aim to collect features during model inference (in this case, reranking) and then compute a salience map over input features using various aggregation strategies. For example, attention rollout (Abnar & Zuidema, 2020) leverages attention scores, grad-sam (Barkan et al., 2021) incorporates gradients, and att-cat (Qiang et al., 2022) combines neuron activations with the other two features.

We tested these methods on the Multi-DocToDial (MD2D) dataset (Feng et al., 2021), which involves a conversational retrieval task. This dataset requires deep understanding of non-trivial text from U.S. state administration driving department documents. In these complex dialogue scenarios, we found the performance of methods that identify the most salient parts of the text deteriorates—achieves performance close to random. Thus, we conclude that the tested post-hoc methods yield plausible results only on datasets that do not require deep document understanding and can rely on surface-level or local information. For instance, **grad-sam** has been evaluated on NLI datasets (involving reviews), which are significantly simpler compared to the dialog-heavy MD2D dataset.

Next, we noticed that prompted LLM can do much better in fine-grained relevance extraction on MD2D. Therefore, we evaluate multiple LLM on our small human 35 sample token-level annotated dataset—a subset of MS-MARCO (Bajaj et al., 2016)—to select best LLM for this task. Evaluation has shown that LLM Gemma 2 (27B)³ is the best performing model for this task, as it matches with human annotations the most.

However, although running retrieval + LLMs to extract fine-grained relevant cues is possible, it is not an efficient approach since the LLM needs to process and extract salient parts from every document in the result. Instead, we would like to employ a lightweight neural model that provides fine-grained relevance cues during the retrieval phase. Unfortunately, there is no such retrieval dataset with fine-grained relevance cues suitable for supervising such a lightweight model.

Thus, we created a new large-scale information retrieval dataset with fine-grained relevance cues by incorporating rationales extracted from Gemma 2 into MS-MARCO documents on token-level granularity; a few examples illustrative examples are shown in Table 4-4. More specifically, we let LLM annotate one relevant passage by letting it select the most relevant spans given a query for all 800,000 queries present in MS-MARCO. The distribution of extracted spans per example starts from 1 span (62.5%), 2 spans (32.2%), 3 spans (4%) up to maximum of 24 spans.

This dataset provides supervision that can be used to train retrieval models to simultaneously a) predict which document is relevant and b) what concretely in the given document is relevant, effectively distilling information knowledge from Gemma into our lightweight retrieval model proposed in the next section.

Table 4-4: Example of token supervision generated by Gemma 2 27B.

Query	Passage (extracted fine-grained cues are bold)
what is community legal service	to make it easier for the public to get advice and legal help, the community legal service brings together organizations offering advice and legal services into local networks
how long to sauté potatoes	for the potatoes. blanch the diced potatoes in the boiling water for 30 seconds and drain in a colander so the steam can escape. on a high heat, in a large frying pan, sauté the diced potatoes in the oil, season with salt and pepper and cook for 4–5 minutes , stirring every minute until golden brown.
how many days to defrost	how many days does it take to defrost a turkey in the refrigerator? defrosting a turkey in the refrigerator will take approximately 3 to 4 days , depending on the size of your turkey. allow one day of thawing in the refrigerator for every 4 pounds of turkey . continue reading below.

4.3.2 Description of the method and model architectures

Our approach utilizes state-of-the-art information retrieval model ColBERTv2 (Santhanam et al., 2022). Unlike Gemma-2, this approach pre-indexes documents, and only lightweight similarity function is used during retrieval. In particular, it encodes each document separately into matrix E_d , producing an embedding vector $E_{d,j}$ for each token j in a document d . Similarly, query is encoded with matrix E_q (where E_{q_i} is an i -th vector in this matrix). For a document d and query q , ColBERT’s interaction mechanism computes relevance score for each pair by **finding best matching document token for each query token** and sums the corresponding values:

³ <https://huggingface.co/google/gemma-2-27b-it>

$$S_{q,d} := \sum_{i \in |E_q|} \max_{j \in |E_d|} E_{q_i}^T \cdot E_{d_j}$$

The core idea of our approach is to utilize ColBERT’s interaction mechanism orthogonally. That means we **find best matching query token for each document token**. Followed by the application of an element-wise sigmoid activation function, it results in a probability for each document token, predicting the likelihood that a concrete document token is relevant

$$\hat{r}_d = \sigma \left(\max_{i \in |E_q|} E_{q_i}^T \cdot E_{d_j} \right)$$

Using the annotated dataset with fine-grained relevance cues r_d from LLM, we can supervise our modified model using Binary Cross-entropy:

$$L_2 = \text{BCE}(\hat{r}_d, r_d)$$

Following the distillation mechanism of ColBERTv2, the L_1 loss is Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence between the (binary) probabilities of cross-encoder (precomputed on training data by original work authors) and ColBERT model probabilities, computed by the softmax normalization of $S_{q,d'}$ across minibatch candidates d' . The final Loss is weighted combination of L_1 and L_2

$$L = L_1 + \lambda L_2$$

where λ controls the influence of the extraction loss. Note that L_2 is only a function of the ground-truth document, for which we previously extracted relevant cues using Gemma 2.

In vanilla ColBERT, both document and query vectors are normalized for unit length, hence their dot product is exactly a cosine similarity function. A limitation of using cosine similarity with sigmoid is that L2-normalized embeddings constrain scores to interval $[-1,1]$, making the model’s predictions consistently uncertain, and also limiting the model flexibility (e.g., for 40 query vectors, the maximum score can be 40 and minimum -40). The next section presents modifications to remove this constraint while keeping the retrieval setup intact, allowing for more flexible scoring.

Specifically, instead of sharing the same encodings $E_{(\cdot)}$ across tasks, we propose to separate embeddings that are computed for retrieval $E_{(\cdot)}^R$ and interpretability $E_{(\cdot)}^I$, while keeping the underlying BERT encoder shared. Naturally, the retrieval embeddings $E_{(\cdot)}^R$ are used to compute the passage-query relevance score, while $E_{(\cdot)}^I$ are used to compute the probability for each passage token to be relevant to the query—producing saliency scores for interpretability.

4.3.2.1 Architecture A – Embedding de-normalization

Although it is not possible to turn off the normalization of embeddings as the retrieval framework expects them to be normalized for efficient retrieval, it is possible to store the magnitude of each embedding vector just before normalization to make the normalization step reversible. The normalized embeddings $E_d^R = E_d$ are stored in the index. To recover richer representations for explanation, the L2 norm $\| E_{d_i} \|^2$ is stored during indexing, allowing the reconstruction of scaled embeddings during inference:

$$E_{d_i}^I = E_{d_i} \cdot \| E_{d_i} \|^2 \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, \text{len}(d)$$

Query embeddings for retrieval E_q^R are after encoding normalized, while interpretability embeddings E_q^I are used directly. While this can be seen as extending each token embedding vector by one dimension, the index increases in size by a factor of $(h + 1)/h$.

4.3.2.2 Architecture B – Separate linear transformation

Another approach is to use a different linear transformation to down-project the BERT encoded sequences. As the encoded representation has higher dimensionality, it should be able to capture the information needed to perform

both tasks. To put it into different perspective, this approach is much less restrictive, as the representation for interpretability are not computed from representations for retrieval, nor the other way around. This enables much better performance possibilities. However, this comes at a cost: the index must be significantly larger. More concretely, the representation for both retrieval and interpretability is stored into the index for each document token. As both vectors have the same dimensionality, the index is two times larger. During inference, retrieval is performed using the vectors for retrieval and vectors for interpretability are loaded afterwards for top-k retrieved documents.

Mathematically, the embeddings for retrieval are obtained by down-projecting encoded sequences using weight matrix

$$\widehat{E}_{(\cdot)}^R = BERT(\cdot)W_1$$

which are further normalized to produce final retrieval embeddings $E_{(\cdot)}^R$. Embeddings for interpretability are obtained using different weight matrix

$$E_{(\cdot)}^I = BERT(\cdot)W_2.$$

4.3.2.3 Architecture C – Non-linear embeddings transformation

The proposed architecture avoids storing extra vectors in the index. Like the first approach, it derives interpretability embeddings from retrieval embeddings, but instead of simple scaling, it uses a feed-forward neural network for transformation. This introduces sequential dependency while offering greater expressivity. Only the FFN weights need to be stored, keeping index size unchanged. Though more computationally demanding, it's applied only to top-k documents, making it efficient. However, the model remains limited due to the sequential nature of task-specific representations.

Embeddings are later retrieved from index for documents and computed online for a query, and used to compute embeddings for interpretability using FFN

$$E_d^I = E_d^R + FFN(E_d^R),$$

where FFN is two-layer fully connected network

$$FFN(E) = ReLU(EW_1)W_2$$

$W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{h \times h_2}$ is up-projection matrix and $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{h_2 \times h}$ is down-projection matrix. Dropout is used after each linear layer during the training.

4.3.3 Experimental results

To evaluate retrieval performance, we use the standard Recall@10 metric commonly applied in information retrieval tasks. Recall@10 measures the proportion of relevant documents retrieved among the top 10 results. Formally, it is defined as:

$$\text{Recall@10} = \frac{|\{\text{Relevant}\} \cap \{\text{Retrieved}_{10}\}|}{|\{\text{Relevant}\}|}$$

The evaluation is performed at the token level. We compute the F1-score between the model predictions and the token-level relevance annotations (provided by humans or LLMs). The F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall:

$$F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

where

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{|\text{Predicted} \cap \text{Relevant}|}{|\text{Predicted}|}, \quad \text{Recall} = \frac{|\text{Predicted} \cap \text{Relevant}|}{|\text{Relevant}|}.$$

Along with the training dataset, we have generated the evaluation dataset using the same approach as training one. The official small development set was used. It includes only 6,938 unique queries as some of the queries were paired with multiple passages. So, the development set was sub-sampled to include only unique queries, and the fine-grained relevance information was extracted only for them.

To enable evaluation of retrieval performance under constrained computational resources, a sub-sampled version of the MS MARCO passage collection was constructed. This subset includes all 6,938 passages annotated as relevant for at least one development query, along with an additional 6,938 randomly sampled passages. To enhance diversity, half of the sampled passages originate from the training dataset, while the other half are drawn from the set of documents that were not used during training. This approach facilitates retrieval evaluation without the need to index the full MS MARCO collection, which contains approximately 8 million passages.

To evaluate model plausibility – how well it aligns with human predictions – we use the small dataset of 35 samples used to evaluate LLMs for the fine-grained extraction task. It should be emphasized, that even when evaluation dataset contains only 35 passage-query pairs, each pair consists of many classification data-points, considering the task of deciding if the token is or is not relevant. More specifically, it translates to around 2200 classification samples, depending on a used tokenizer.

To explore the impact of initialization on model performance, we train each architecture from two distinct starting points. The first is the ColBERT checkpoint⁴, which has been pretrained for retrieval tasks. This initialization introduces a strong inductive bias towards effective retrieval, and the training objective is to extend the model's capabilities to fine-grained relevance extraction while retaining its retrieval performance. The second initialization uses the general-purpose BERT model⁵, which lacks retrieval-specific pretraining. This setup enables the model to explore a broader solution space and potentially converge to an optimal representation that jointly supports both retrieval and fine-grained relevance extraction. However, this setup requires more training steps to achieve comparable performance.

The aim of this work is to evaluate three research questions, corresponding to the following subchapters:

(RQ1) Firstly, we investigate whether using fine-grained relevance supervision leads to a stronger model focus on nuanced relevance signals, making the model interpretable by design.

(RQ2) Secondly, we evaluate the relationship between the fine-grained extraction and document retrieval performance regarding different model architectures.

(RQ3) Thirdly, we examine whether providing a more detailed supervision signal reduces the number of training steps required to achieve a well-performing retrieval model.

⁴ Used ColBERT checkpoint: <https://huggingface.co/colbert-ir/colbertv1.9>

⁵ Used BERT checkpoint: <https://huggingface.co/google-bert/bert-base-uncased>

4.3.3.1 Fine-Grained Extraction Performance

Figure 4-8: Progress of training using de-normalization architecture training from pretrained ColBERT

Figure 4-8 illustrates extraction performance across training checkpoints using precision-recall curves. Darker lines correspond to earlier checkpoints (closer to initialization), while brighter lines represent later stages of training. The proportion of relevant tokens in the dataset is approximately 0.37, observable as the precision at full recall. A baseline approach assigning random scores to tokens is shown in red; even the initial model outperforms this baseline. Since checkpoints are sampled at uniform intervals, the greater spacing between early curves indicates rapid initial learning, while the reduced spacing between later curves indicates slower improvement and the onset of convergence.

Table 4-5: Evaluation of extraction performance of all proposed model architectures on development dataset

Model Architecture	Initialization	F1-score
Non-linear embeddings transformation	BERT	0.7038
	ColBERT	0.7093
Separate linear transformation	BERT	0.7067
	ColBERT	0.6775
Embedding de-normalization	BERT	0.6816
	ColBERT	0.6719
Retrieval Only	BERT	0.5008

The evaluation of various LLMs on 35 samples to decide which model is best for extraction revealed that Gemma 2 (27B) matches with human annotations the best. The F1-Score for this match was 0.7045, indicating a substantial overlap. During the evaluation of the trained models, we have been able to achieve comparable F1-Scores, which are derived directly during retrieval rather than asking LM to provide them. It should be emphasized that we have selected the best F-1 Score regarding all possible thresholding values, therefore calibrated the model on an evaluation dataset. Table 4-5 presents the evaluation results for all architectures. The best performance on fine-grained relevance extraction was achieved by the *Non-linear embeddings transformation* model initialized from ColBERT. Although the retrieval-only model was not trained for token-level extraction, its architecture allows computing token-level scores via its interaction mechanism, providing a meaningful baseline. Table 4-5 also includes the architecture without the extraction component for comparison.

3 - what is paranoid sc

paranoid schizophrenia is a psychotic disorder . in - depth information on symptoms , causes , treatment of paranoid schizophrenia . find this pin and more on schizophrenia by healthy place . paranoid schizophrenia is a psychotic disorder . in - depth information on symptoms , causes , treatment of paranoid schizophrenia . see more

4 - treatment of varicose veins in legs

ca yen ne pepper . ca yen ne pepper is considered a miracle treatment for varico se veins . being a very rich source of vitamin c and bio fl av ono ids , it increases blood circulation and ease s the pain of cong ested , swollen veins . add one tea sp oon of ca yen ne pepper powder to a cup of hot water and stir it well .

5 - what is prime rate in canada

what is the prime rate ? in canada , the prime rate is a guide line interest rate used by banks on loans for their most credit worthy , best , or prime clients . the prime rate rises and falls with the e bb and flow of the canadian economy , influenced significantly by the overnight rate , which is set by the bank of canada .

Figure 4-9: Three examples of fine-grained relevance extraction of the best performing model.

Figure 4-9 presents fine-grained extraction examples produced by the best-performing model: the *Non-linear embeddings transformation* architecture initialized from ColBERT, which achieved an F1-score of 0.7093. Each example is sampled from the MS MARCO small development set, with scores obtained during inference. In the first example, the query asks for a definition of *paranoid schizophrenia*. The model assigns higher scores to the beginning of the passage containing the definition, aligning well with the fine-grained LLM-based annotations (highlighted in bold). The remainder of the passage, while related to the topic, is less relevant to the query and receives appropriately lower scores. The final phrase, "see more", is irrelevant and correctly assigned the lowest score. In the second example, two annotated spans are both assigned the highest scores, while an intermediate sentence—less relevant but not entirely off-topic—receives intermediate scores, appropriately ranked above the least relevant part discussing dosage. Similar score distributions and alignment with annotations are evident in the third example.

4.3.3.2 Relationship Between Model Plausibility and Document Retrieval

Figure 4-10: Evaluation of fine-grained extraction and document retrieval during training for all proposed architectures.

So far, we have only discussed the fine-grained extraction performance, however, as this performance is increasing, the document retrieval performance might decrease. For each training run, ten checkpoints are uniformly sampled over the course of training, with the final checkpoint always included. Since the training durations vary across runs, the progress is normalized per run. Figure 4-10 highlights the set of Pareto optimal solutions, representing non-dominated trade-offs between fine-grained and document-level performance. Figure 4-10 serves as a reference throughout the subsequent evaluation.

First, consider the training of *EDN-b- λ 0*, initialized from BERT with fine-grained supervision disabled ($\lambda = 0$). Training begins with low performance on both tasks. Recall@50 improves rapidly in the early stages and then plateaus, but fine-grained relevance prediction remains poor. This suggests that optimizing only for retrieval does not transfer to the extraction task—contrary to the initial hypothesis that progress in one task would benefit the other. Interestingly, the best checkpoint from this run performs only slightly worse in retrieval than the ColBERT-initialized models.

Second, the *EDN* architecture is most affected by the trade-off between retrieval and extraction. For example, *EDN-c- λ 80*, initialized from ColBERT, begins training with high retrieval performance (Recall@50 \approx 0.98) but drops to 0.83 as the extraction F1 score increases to 0.68. This pattern repeats across other EDN runs with higher λ values, indicating that stronger extraction supervision consistently harms retrieval.

Third, the *SLT* architecture manages to retain document retrieval performance while learning extraction. *SLT-c- λ 60* reaches an F1 of about 0.677—comparable to *EDN-c- λ 80*—while Recall@50 decreases only slightly (from 0.9800 to 0.9712). Although it doesn't reach the highest extraction score, it appears on the Pareto front, with the final checkpoints achieving a good balance between tasks. In contrast, *SLT-b- λ 80*, initialized from BERT, achieves better extraction performance but performs worse in retrieval, likely due to the absence of retrieval-specific initialization or the stronger extraction emphasis from the high λ .

Lastly, the *FFN* architecture performs the strongest overall, contributing multiple Pareto-optimal checkpoints. *FFN-c- λ 60*, initialized from ColBERT, maintains strong retrieval while achieving the best extraction performance.

However, *FFN-b- λ 60*, initialized from BERT with the same λ , underperforms in retrieval (peaking at Recall@50 = 0.4608), possibly due to insufficient training time. A longer run, *FFN-b- λ 60 long*, continued to improve extraction but not retrieval, suggesting that extraction gains came at the cost of retrieval regardless of training duration.

To conclude, contrary to the initial hypothesis, none of the BERT-initialized runs surpassed the retrieval performance of the model trained solely for document retrieval. The trade-off between fine-grained extraction and document retrieval is most pronounced in models where interpretability embeddings are computed from retrieval embeddings—particularly in the *EDN* architecture, and to a lesser extent in *FFN*. As a result, no *EDN*-based model achieved Pareto optimality. In contrast, the *FFN* architecture exhibits the weakest trade-off, therefore contributing multiple checkpoints to the Pareto front, including the long training run initialized from BERT, which achieved the highest fine-grained extraction performance, and the ColBERT-initialized run, which reached slightly lower extraction performance but substantially higher retrieval performance. The SLT architecture appears in the Pareto front with a ColBERT-initialized model that preserves retrieval performance despite not excelling in extraction. The unmodified ColBERT model also belongs to the Pareto front, achieving the highest retrieval score while lacking fine-grained extraction capability.

4.3.3.3 Impact of Supervision Detail on Training Efficiency

We hypothesized that incorporating fine-grained supervision would reduce the number of training steps required to obtain a well-performing retrieval model, as the model would benefit from a richer supervision signal. However, we were unable to consistently validate this hypothesis. The only partial evidence supporting it was observed in one scenario, depicted in Figure 4-11 where the model with fine-grained extraction enabled slightly outperformed the retrieval-only model. Nevertheless, the improvement in recall@10 was marginal—approximately 0.02—and occurred during the initial rapid phase of performance increase. Evaluation across all other checkpoints showed that the retrieval-only model consistently achieved better retrieval performance.

We plan to evaluate the constrained retrieval scenario by focusing on model performance at convergence rather than immediately after initialization. Specifically, we aim to limit the number of training samples to approximately 2,500 (compared to current ~600,000) and investigate whether incorporating fine-grained supervision can yield a better-performing retrieval model under such restricted training conditions.

4.3.4 Summary and future directions

In support of ELOQUENCE’s objective to develop interpretable and robust dialogue systems, this section outlines key contributions and future directions for enhancing token-level interpretability in neural retrieval. Recognizing the scarcity of fine-grained supervision data, a new large-scale dataset was constructed from MS MARCO using annotations generated by the Gemma 2 language model, which closely aligns with human relevance spans. The resulting 792,448 query-passage pairs offer a valuable resource for learning fine-grained token-level relevance—a foundation for interpretable dialogue and retrieval tasks.

Building on this, the proposed FGR-ColBERT architecture introduces token-level supervision into the ColBERT retrieval framework via an auxiliary extraction loss. Multiple architectural variants were explored to balance retrieval effectiveness with interpretability and computational efficiency. Empirical results demonstrate that token-level supervision substantially improves alignment with human judgments, achieving superior extraction accuracy despite using significantly fewer parameters than the teacher model (Gemma 2).

Figure 4-11: Evaluation of retrieval throughout the training initialized from BERT for model with disabled fine-grained extraction (baseline) and model jointly trained for fine-grained extraction and document retrieval.

A Pareto analysis reveals that this interpretability gain comes with only minimal loss in retrieval performance — highlighting FGR-ColBERT's capacity to serve dual goals of efficient retrieval and transparent reasoning, both central to ELOQUENCE. Future work will extend this approach to multilingual benchmarks, reduce index redundancy through embedding transformations, and scale supervision with more complex candidate sets. These steps further ELOQUENCE’s mission to deliver multilingual, efficient, and explainable language technologies that generalize across languages and domains.

4.4 CopyLM: Enabling Span-Level Reuse in Language Generation

4.4.1 Motivation

Assistants based on LLMs work very well on automating repetitive routine tasks⁶. However, the LLMs themselves are quite inefficient at processing the repeated information they have already encoded in the past.

LLMs based on transformer architecture always predict one token at a time. For example, given prompt “Do you prefer a hot chocolate or a cold drink instead”, the language model answering either “hot | chocolate” or “cold | drink” must compute the probability for the next-token prediction twice, as the answers are composed of two tokens (tokens are separated by | for clarity). This involves calling the whole transformer network twice. The necessity of computing the probability for the next token comes from the product rule of probability and the autoregressive factorization of the language model:

$$P(x) = P_{\theta}(x_0) \prod_{i=1}^n P_{\theta}(x_i | x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_0).$$

⁶ <https://www.k2view.com/blog/llm-powered-autonomous-agents/#K2view-empowers-LLM-powered-autonomous-agents>

Here, $\mathbf{x} = x_0 x_1 \dots x_n$ is a sequence of tokens of length $n+1$, $\forall i: x_i$ is a token, and P_θ is the language model function parametrized by the neural network model.

However, the assumption of autoregressive factorization prevents the model from repeating whole terms, it once generated (i.e., in timestep i they exist as a subsequence of in the context sequence $x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_0$). To regenerate these terms, the model needs to predict them token-by-token. Firstly, this is inefficient, the language model should be able to regenerate parts of the input (**an input span**) just with a single step, should it find it probable. Secondly, this increases the theoretical possibility of hallucination—since the probability of error rises exponentially—if the model must repeat a sequence of 100 tokens, even though the probability of not making an error for every token is very high, say $\epsilon = 0.99$, then the probability of correct repetition of 100 tokens is just $\epsilon^{100} = 0.37$!

As a remedy, we propose several parametrizations, which modify a language model in such a way that it allows the model to copy a *span of any size* it has already generated in the past in a single step. This is different from past work (Singh, Xia, Qin, Yarmohammadi, & Durme, 2020) (Eric & Manning, 2017), which focused on copying only a single token at a time. Our inspiration draws from our past work on Extractive Question Answering (Fajcik, Jon, & Smrz, 2021), where we proposed state-of-the-art techniques for probabilistic span modeling.

Figure 4-12: Proportion of assistant turns where at least 1 n-gram could be copied from the previous context of conversation.

Furthermore, we motivate the problem by analyzing WildChat (Zhao, et al., 2024)—a recent dataset of 1 million ChatGPT-human natural conversations (where about 800K conversations are in English). In Figure 4-12, we analyze the turns of the assistant (Chat-GPT) in the dataset. Precisely, we count the number of cases where the response of the assistant contained at least a single n-gram (a sequence of n tokens, e.g., in figure column 3, n=3), which was previously contained in the conversation context (already encoded by the model). We find that in more than 80% of cases, a 2-gram could be copied, and perhaps more importantly, in around 20% of cases, a 10-gram could be copied—possibly saving at least 9 inference steps in this assistant turn.

4.4.2 Method for Span-Modeling

In an autoregressive language model, the probability model $P_\theta(x_i | x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_0)$ is parametrized by encoding the past tokens $x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_0$ into a vector embedding $\mathbf{h}_{i-1} = f_\theta(x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_0)$. Using the vector \mathbf{h}_{i-1} , the language model computes a categorical distribution $P_\theta(x_i | x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_0) = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{h}_{i-1})$.

We leverage these representations to propose three kinds of language model (LM) extensions that allow span modelling. In all cases, we will extend a pre-trained language model with a set of newly initialized parameters θ_{span} , that will leverage the final transformer layer representations $\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_0; \mathbf{h}_1; \dots; \mathbf{h}_n]$; $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$. From now on, we will refer to the LM extension as the **span head**.

The span head computes the probability distribution over all possible spans in the past. For example, if the past contains n tokens, and we consider span size of at least 2 tokens, span head allows to quantify $\frac{n \times (n-1)}{2}$ probabilities of span distribution that correspond to valid spans. The span head often considers the assumption of independence (Aoi) of span start and span end, formally $P_\theta(x_i^{start}, x_i^{end} | \cdot) = P_\theta(x_i^{start} | \cdot) P_\theta(x_i^{end} | \cdot)$. This simplification leads

to computing only n scores of ends, and $n - 1$ scores of start (so $2n - 1$) probabilities in total. Outer product of these computes the joint start-end probability with $n \times (n - 1)$ coefficients (the end-before-start cases, and single-token cases, can be masked, hence only $\frac{n \times (n-1)}{2}$ will be non-masked coefficients). Aol reduces the computational burden at the cost of making an error due to the simplifying assumption.

Predict-then-compute approach first computes the probability of the special *[span]* symbol, and only then computes the span head. This releases the computation burden of span head, at the cost of allowing error propagation. If *[span]* symbol is predicted, but the model has low span-confidence, it could lead to wrong span prediction. The span head computation includes Aol.

Direct compute approach computes the span head in every timestep. This prevents error propagation but increases computational burden. Additionally, this approach uses more data, as it also obtains loss gradient in cases where no span was predicted in the ground truth—in these cases, the span score of each span is minimized. The span head computation includes Aol.

Direct joint compute approach is similar to the previous *direct compute approach*. However, in this case, the span head *does not* include Aol. Instead, we design an efficient computational method to compute the joint probability space $P_{\theta}(x_i^{start}, x_i^{end} | \cdot)$ directly.

4.4.2.1 Predict-Then-Compute

The Predict-Then-Compute (PTC) method extends model vocabulary with a single [copy] token. The model is trained to predict the [copy] token using the standard maximum likelihood objective for language models \mathcal{L}_{lm} . Precisely, if the original labels in the training dataset for the model were of the form “a | b | c | b | c | d”⁷, where | is a token separator, we modify them to be “a | b | c | [copy] | - | d”, where - is a label ignored in the loss (i.e., the loss is not computed in that timestep). At test time, we use standard decoding methods to use the original language model.

In training, we compute span head only for the timesteps with [copy] token, whereas in test time, we compute span head when [copy] token is predicted. The span head is computed as follows. Recall the representation $\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_0; \mathbf{h}_1; \dots; \mathbf{h}_n]$ of all model timesteps. We project these with 3 linear projects $\mathbf{H}^{past}, \mathbf{H}^{start}, \mathbf{H}^{end} = \mathbf{W}_{past}\mathbf{H}, \mathbf{W}_{start}\mathbf{H}, \mathbf{W}_{end}\mathbf{H}$ ⁸.

Now consider timestep t with copy token as a label.

$$P_{\theta}(X_i^{start} | x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_0) = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{H}^{past}[:, t] \mathbf{h}_{t-1}^{start})$$

$$P_{\theta}(X_i^{end} | x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_0) = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{H}^{past}[:, t] \mathbf{h}_{t-1}^{end})$$

Where $\mathbf{H}^{past}[:, t] = [\mathbf{h}_0^{past}; \mathbf{h}_1^{past}; \dots; \mathbf{h}_{t-1}^{past}]$.

In training, each [span] token is associated with span indices [a,b]. The model is trained to maximize the start a, and end b using standard maximum likelihood objective—corresponding to loss functions $\mathcal{L}_{start}, \mathcal{L}_{end}$. The losses for each [span] position in the minibatch are averaged. During training, the total loss is thus composed of three components $\mathcal{L} = \lambda \mathcal{L} + (1 - \lambda)(\mathcal{L}_{start} + \mathcal{L}_{end})/2$. The probabilities of single-token spans are always explicitly set to 0.

4.4.2.2 Direct Compute

Differently from the Predict-then-compute approach, Direct Compute (DC) approach: (i) keeps the original vocabulary, (ii) computes the span head in every timestep the same way. However, instead of having a separate loss for start/end probability supervision, we extend the output vocabulary with span logits. In training, we do not use all logits—in order to avoid materializing matrix of start/end scores for every timestep which has $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$

⁷ Note that model inputs are kept unchanged. We only change output labels for span-based LM.

⁸ We also include biases but omit them in formulas for brevity.

computation/memory complexity for the context of size n —but instead sample K starts and K ends according to current $P_\theta(X_i^{start}|\cdot), P_\theta(X_i^{end}|\cdot)$. We ensure that the ground-truth choice is sampled in training. Formally:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{l}_t^{lm} &= \mathbf{W}_{lm} \mathbf{h}_{t-1} \\ \mathbf{l}_t^{start} &= \mathbf{H}^{past}[:, t] \mathbf{h}_{t-1}^{start} \\ \mathbf{l}_t^{end} &= \mathbf{H}^{past}[:, t] \mathbf{h}_{t-1}^{end} \end{aligned}$$

Assume index sets $\mathbf{c}^{start} \sim^K P_\theta(X_t^{start}|\cdot), \mathbf{c}^{end} \sim^K P_\theta(X_t^{end}|\cdot)$. The vector of joint logits for these combinations is then $\mathbf{l}_t^{span} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{l}_t^{start}[\mathbf{c}^{start}] \oplus \mathbf{l}_t^{end}[\mathbf{c}^{end}])$. Here $[\cdot]$ denotes vector indexing, \oplus denotes outer summation, and vec flattens the matrix into a vector. The final logit vector in training is then given by their concatenation $\mathbf{l}_t = [\mathbf{l}_t^{lm}, \mathbf{l}_t^{span}]$. The joint span-lm probability space is then computed as

$$P_\theta^{span-lm}(X_i | x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_0) = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{l}_i).$$

Recall the labeling from the previous section “a | b | c | [copy] | - | d”. Here, a, b, c, and d were regular tokens, as objective maximized their probability. In case of “-”, the computation of loss is skipped like before. However, if the label is [copy], we maximize the probability at the position which corresponds to a combination of correct start and correct end logit in the normalized probability vector. At test time, we compute the full joint space $P_\theta^{span}(X_i^{start}, X_i^{end} | x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_0) = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{l}_i^{span})$ in every timestep i . We only append the highest candidate span score to the \mathbf{l}_t^{lm} vector in every timestep. Hence, the model can only predict either the most probable span or a token from the vocabulary.

4.4.2.3 Direct Joint Compute

Differently from the DC approach, Direct Joint Compute (DJT) computes joint probability distribution $P_\theta^{span-lm}(X_i^{start}, X_i^{end} | x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_0)$, instead of relying on the assumption of independence (Aol). Similarly to DC, we encode past inputs as \mathbf{H}^{past} , and current timestep as $\mathbf{h}_{t-1}^{start}, \mathbf{h}_{t-1}^{end}$. Differently from DC, we increase the dimensionality of all span head projections ($\mathbf{W}_{past}, \mathbf{W}_{start}, \mathbf{W}_{end}$) $n=4$ times. Next, we compute the *representations* for each *start*, and *end*. Notice that in DC, every *start* (and *end*) is represented by a single score. In DJC, inspired by the concept of Multi-head attention, we split vectors in the $\mathbf{H}^{past}, \mathbf{h}_{t-1}^{start}, \mathbf{h}_{t-1}^{end}$ into $h=64$ heads $\mathbf{H}^{past} = [\mathbf{H}_0^{past}; \mathbf{H}_1^{past}; \dots; \mathbf{H}_{h-1}^{past}]$ (analogically for vectors $\mathbf{h}_{t-1}^{start}, \mathbf{h}_{t-1}^{end}$), where $\mathbf{H}_i^{past} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_h}, d_h = \frac{d}{h}, d_h \ll d$ and $;$ is a concatenation operator. Next, we compute a similarity vector for i -th head similarly as \mathbf{l}_t^{pos} (where $pos \in \{start, end\}$) in DC Approach. Specifically,

$$\mathbf{s}_{t,i}^{pos} = \mathbf{H}_i^{past}[:, t] \mathbf{h}_{t-1,i}^{pos}$$

Therefore matrix $\mathbf{S}_t^{pos} = \{\mathbf{s}_{t,0}^{pos}; \mathbf{s}_{t,1}^{pos}; \dots; \mathbf{s}_{t,h}^{pos}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times h}$ contains representations of every past token $x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_0$ of pos, of size h , for span-prediction in the timestep t . The logits of span are then simply computed as:

$$\mathbf{l}_t^{span} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{S}_t^{start} (\mathbf{S}_t^{end})^\top).$$

The joint probability is computed in the same way as in DC approach. However, notice that in training, where this span-space computation needs to be done in every timestep, this again has $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$ computation/memory complexity. Unfortunately, we cannot compute independent probabilities for sampling the hard candidates from the representations \mathbf{S}_t^{pos} directly. Thus, during training, we just use the uniform random subset of start/end positions as the candidates $\mathbf{c}^{start}, \mathbf{c}^{end}$ (always including the ground truth position candidates). The rest of the training follows DC approach. In test-time we compute the full joint space in every timestep and append only highest scoring span score to vocabulary logits, same as for DC approach.

4.4.3 Experimental Setup

4.4.3.1 Dataset Construction

We construct a training dataset from WildChat (Zhao, et al., 2024). Specifically, we focus on assistant turns—we prompt the model with previous history and train it to predict the assistant turn—this corresponds to our training example.

We apply additional filtering steps: (i) only select samples that (i) are in English, (ii) fit into a 1024-token window of GPT-2 (Radford, et al., 2019). Then we exhaustively map the substrings in the assistant turn to their prefixes, always finding the longest common substring.

This is illustrated in Figure 4-13. Here, we have labels as language modeling token ids (denoting we should predict token 1 in the first timestep, etc.), 999 is the id of [SPAN] token, and -100 is the label of an ignored token (no cross entropy is computed at this position). The minimum span length is 2. Triplet 999,-100,-100 (repeated twice) represents the copy of subsequence [1,2,3] (associated with span [0,3] twice). Next, the last [999,-100] represents the copy of span subsequence [4,4] associated with span indices [9,11]. From this supervision, the model implementation is informed when to maximize the probability [SPAN] token, and compute the span head in the PTC model, or when to maximize the correct span probability in other cases. Notice that there is no loss computed in subsequent steps extending the span. Additionally, we also keep track of span indices for each [SPAN] token.

```
# Test case 6: Complex scenario with multiple and nested repeats
labels = [1, 2, 3, 1, 2, 3, 1, 2, 3, 4, 4, 4, 4]
expected = [1, 2, 3, 999, -100, -100, 999, -100, -100, 4, 4, 999, -100]
expected_spans = [[0, 3], [0, 3], [9, 11]]
```

Figure 4-13: Example of label transformation method, used as a supervision for CopyLM.

This process resulted in 441,469/2,000/4,000 training, validation, and test set examples.

4.4.4 Training setup

We extend GPT-2 (Radford, et al., 2019)(137M parameters) with a span head. We continuously train the model starting from a pre-trained checkpoint on Huggingface. For training and evaluation, we use LLM Foundry⁹. We use AdamW optimizer (Loshchilov & Hutter, 2019), no weight decay, gradient norm clipping at 2.0, minibatch size of 128, cosine learning rate schedule with 10% warmup and 75,000 training steps in total.

⁹ <https://github.com/mosaicml/llm-foundry>

4.4.5 Preliminary Evaluation

4.4.5.1 Quality of Span-Prediction

To evaluate the quality of the span-prediction module, we first analyze the accuracy of predictions of ground-truth spans on validation data. Note that we only consider the timesteps where span appeared (i.e., with GT label [span]), and this metric does not consider other timesteps, when the span could have been predicted, but it should not be predicted according to the ground truth.

In Figure 4-14 we analyze the accuracy of predicting the start of the ground-truth span. We compare Predict-Then-Compute (PTC), Direct Compute (DC), and Direct Joint Compute (DJC) models. Note that DC samples “hard” negatives from the current model of independent span start/span end distribution (denoted as *hardn<count>*). Also note that if the count is, say, 30, we sample 30 starts and 30 ends, thus having the $30 \times (30 - 1) / 2 = 435$ candidates in

Figure 4-14: Span start accuracy across different model assumptions during training. Left: full training run, Right: close-up.

total. In DJC, we sample negatives at random, thus, we use suffix *randn<count>*. Analyzing our results: (i) we observe that joint models achieve best span start accuracy with around 200 random negatives (runs *DJC_rand230* and *DJC_rand200*) (ii) we tried using random negatives in DC (run *DC_randn200*), and see inferior results to DJC, and similar to using just 30 hard negatives (*DC_hardn30*). Exactly the opposite trend holds when using a smaller number of negatives, such as 50. We observe that (iii) DJC (run *DJC_randn50*) fails to achieve good accuracy, in comparison to DC run (run *DC_randn50*). This indicates that DJC needs more hard negatives in order to achieve good performance, but at the same time, it can achieve better performance overall. Lastly, the performance of PTC (iv) is inferior to DC or DJC in comparable settings. Whether the larger amount of hard negatives could improve PTC or DC remains an open question for now.

Next, in Figure 4-15 we analyze the accuracy of ground-truth end prediction. This metric is likely too strict, as the model might simply aim to copy shorter spans than annotated, i.e., the task of modeling end probability has higher overall probability distribution entropy, as when compared to the start distribution.

Figure 4-15: Span end accuracy across different model assumptions during training. Left: full training run, Right: close-up.

We observe: (i) the opposite trend to Figure 4-14 for the best PTC, DC, and DJC runs. Specifically, the PTC dominates

the end prediction. We conjecture this might be caused by (a) the fact that PTC is only supervised in [SPAN]-labelled timesteps, hence being more confident in the longest-common-span substring generated by our supervision. Alternatively (b), the fact that PTC is supervised independently for start/end probability distribution, as compared to DC, which combines the start/end logits and optimizes joint logits, might play a role. We will analyze the accuracy based on span length in future work.

To dissect the reverse trends of Figure 4-14 and Figure 4-15, in Figure 4-16 we finally analyze the accuracy of span prediction (i.e., ground-truth span is predicted correctly if and only if both its start and end are predicted correctly).

Figure 4-16: Span accuracy across different model assumptions during training. Left: full training run (Right: close-up)

As we expected based on our past work (Fajcik, Jon, & Smrz, 2021), in the actual span prediction, the assumption of independence (Aoi) plays a major role. If the model considers Aoi, it can predict the start of one span candidate, but the end of a different span candidate. This problem tends to be more severe in high-entropy cases (i.e., in cases where there are many likely candidates considered in the probability distribution). We observe that (i) DJC dominates the other approaches even with just 50 random negatives. Next, we see that (ii) DC and PTC perform about the same.

Lastly, we comment on the dynamics of the PTC curve at the start of the training (visible in all Figures in this section). We observed that the models first start to optimize the span accuracy, which produces a large error at the start of the training (fast-increasing purple curve). However, during this time, the perplexity of the LM is impacted, and at some point, the optimization switches strategy to optimize the perplexity instead of accuracy (hence the drop in accuracy). After a brief training time, the optimization continues to improve both metrics, LM perplexity and accuracy.

4.4.5.2 Qualitative samples from Copy-LM approaches

We include qualitative samples from PTC, DC, and DJC below. In all cases, the samples were obtained using standard ancestral sampling. The prompt for the model is shown in Figure 4-17. The generated spans are **bold** and enclosed in `<sp></sp>` tags.

```

[user]: As an AI language model, can I be your assistant?
[assistant]: As an AI language model, my primary purpose is to assist users by generating human-like text in response to their prompts. While I am happy to assist you in generating text, I cannot serve as a personal assistant to carry out tasks beyond generating text. Is there anything specific you need help with generating text for?
[user]: As an AI language model, you can ask me any question and I'll try your best to answer it for you.
[assistant]: Thank you! Here's my question for you: What is the capital of Peru?
[user]: The API key is associated with a deactivated account.
    
```

Figure 4-17: Example prompt.

```

<sp>assistant |:</sp> Thank you for clarifying, but I have no knowledge or understanding of how<sp> a deactivated account</sp> is customized with the<sp> API key</sp> associated with AOA (Access and Authorization System).<sp> AOA</sp> (Application Object Access) is a standard authorization system used to authenticate users with specific credentials (like<sp> AOA</sp> tokens). It provides access rights to user information, like<sp> AOA</sp> cards or authentication keys.
    
```

Figure 4-18: Generation from PTC model.

|assistant |: Thank you! The API key is associated with a deactivated account, which generates human-like text based on a user's request, but this does not always guarantee a complete solution. Depending on the user's needs and capabilities, there may be specific restrictions placed on the API key. It's important to verify whether the API key is properly authenticated or unlocked before attempting to use the app. Thank you! Here's my question for you: What is the capital of Peru?

Figure 4-19: Generation from DC model.

|assistant |: The API key that is associated with a deactivated account can be found through the website eplucijuushestonenformunvekt.AIPL. Additionally, there is a website accessible under the domain charisa.net that has instructions for generating a user's API key.

Here are some general steps for generating a user's API key. They are as follows:

1. Open the website at your location: This is a API key for the application. They can be accessed right through the URL.
2. Select the application - Select your application as a API key and click on it.
3. After selecting the application, there is a "Generate Your API key" notification button that can be accessed through the mail option of the application.
4. Select the user's API key - Press Alt+T Column to select the API key.
5. After performing the steps listed, the website will generate a user's API key for the application.

By choosing your API key, there is a pathway for the application to assist you in generating text.

Figure 4-20: Generation from DJC model.

4.4.6 Summary and Future Directions

With small GPT-2, we expected the results to be inferior to baseline, due to the fact that span-prediction requires predicting multiple tokens in the future at once (so-called speculative decoding¹⁰), which is known to have inferior performance as compared to next-token prediction models. Secondly, the GPT-2 model can be too small to handle semantically meaningful responses, as is demonstrated with qualitative examples in Section 4.4.5.2.

In the next steps, we (a) still need to do an additional analysis with a versatile small GPT-2 model, and (b) train a larger version of the model (probably a 7B model) that provides meaningful responses. *In former case* (a), we seek to further investigate (i) the effect of negatives on hard negative sampling case, (ii) more efficient way of obtaining negatives than just sampling uniform at random for DJC approach, (iii) soft metrics for span assessment such as token-precision and token-recall and (iv) an effect of non-linear projection, number of heads, and dimensionality expansion for DJC approach.

In spite of slightly inferior results in Figure 4-14 in the case of DJC, our qualitative assessment of generated cases seems to favor the DJC model—the other models seem to suffer from AoI errors, predicting very long spans of text, which is nonsensical in the given context. To confirm this behavior, in the latter case (b), we plan to (i) repeat our best small model experiments with 7B model (probably Llama 3.1-Instruct model) with all three assumptions, and (ii) optimize the implementation to provide a direct FLOPS comparison between the baseline model, and the copy-lm model.

Lastly, we plan to focus on copy-dependent tasks, where the Copy-LM could possibly mitigate the LM hallucination. Firstly, we plan to (i) isolate a subset of WildChat (or possibly another dataset) that focuses on code editing tasks and test it only on this subset. Secondly, we plan to (ii) train our model on the scientific summarization dataset, such as (Docekal, Fajcik, & Smrz, 2024), which allows us to study whether the copy-lm-based summarization model was able to increase the factuality of the generated summaries.

¹⁰ See for example <https://pytorch.org/blog/hitchhikers-guide-speculative-decoding/>.

5 Addressing High-Risk Dialogue Scenarios: Strategies, Resources and Initial Results

This chapter presents a set of methodological strategies, system components, and preliminary results aimed at enabling context-sensitive dialogue generation in high-stakes applications. The chapter begins by introducing Dialog2Flow, a method for automatic dialogue flow extraction that uses action-driven sentence embeddings to infer and represent the underlying structure of conversations (Section 5.1). This technique bridges the gap between free-form language and structured interaction policies, allowing for better monitoring, validation, and eventual control of LLM-driven agents. By identifying functional dialogue acts and mapping them to flows, the method supports interpretability and oversight—both essential in regulated domains.

We then describe our initial experiments towards context-aware dialogue modeling (Section 5.2). Here, we explore and define diverse alternative to formally define and enforce relevant context for LLMs operating in critical settings, concretely within the context of the *NurseLLM* which is part of the Pilot 4 from ELOQUENCE project. Then, we present our initial experiments on next-response generation using LLMs in high-risk dialogue settings (Section 5.3). These experiments investigate the impact of prompting strategies and model scaling, evaluate cross-lingual generalization and performance of different multilingual LLMs, and offer a preliminary examination of the limitations of standard automatic evaluation metrics in clinically sensitive dialogue tasks. These insights contribute directly to ELOQUENCE’s long-term goal of fostering robust dialogue models that can operate reliably under operational, ethical, and regulatory constraints.

Altogether, this chapter consolidates methods and experimental insights aimed at designing dialogue systems that are better suited for high-risk use cases—where explainability, traceability, and error minimization are central to responsible deployment.

5.1 Dialog2Flow: Action-Driven Sentence Embeddings for Automatic Dialogue Flow Extraction

5.1.1 Motivation

Dialogue modeling can be divided into open-domain dialogues and TOD, with the latter focusing on helping users achieve specific tasks (Jurafsky, 2002). In TOD, structured workflows guide agents in assisting users effectively. The preliminary work done by IDIAP explores how to automatically extract such a workflow from a collection of conversational data. Extracting workflows automatically is crucial for enhancing dialogue system design, discourse analysis, data augmentation (Qiu, Wu, Liu, & Xiong., 2022), and training human agents (Sohn, et al., 2023). Additionally, such a type of knowledge can ground LLMs in domain-specific workflows, improving transparency and control (Raghu, Agarwal, & Joshi, 2021; Chen, Lin, Han, & Sun, 2024).

In TODs, *dialog acts* and *slots* are key concepts (Jurafsky, 2002). Dialogue acts represent the speaker’s communicative intent, while slots capture task-specific information. A dialogue action encapsulates both the dialogue act and its corresponding slots, enabling us to view dialogs as sequences of canonical steps that convey both *communicative* and *informative functions*. Thus, Dialog2Flow (D2F) represents a sentence embedding model pre-trained specifically for dialogue flow extraction, a solution capable of producing sentence embeddings into a latent space grouped by representative actions rather than solely by sentence semantics. Next, we briefly describe the model architecture and training methodology.

5.1.2 Method and model architecture

5.1.2.1 Representation Learning Framework

Following common practices (Zhou, et al., 2022; Chen, Kornblith, Norouzi, & Hinton, 2020; Tian, Krishnan, & Isola, 2020; Khosla, et al., 2020), the main components of our framework are:

- **Encoder**, $f(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, which maps x to a representation vector, $\mathbb{x} = f(x)$. Following Sentence-BERT and Dialogue Sentence Embeddings (DSE) (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019), $f(\cdot)$ consists of a BERT-based encoder with a mean pooling strategy trained as a bi-encoder with shared weights (siamese network).

- **Contrastive head**, $g(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^d$, used during training to map representations \mathbf{x} to the space where contrastive loss is applied. Following (Chen, Kornblith, Norouzi, & Hinton, 2020) and DSE, we instantiate $g(\cdot)$ as a multi-layer perceptron with a single hidden layer $z = g(x) = \text{ReLU}(x, W_1)W_2$ where $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$.
- **Similarity measure**, $\text{sim}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})$ used to learn the representation is cosine similarity. Thus, similarity is then measured only by the angle between \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} , making our latent space geometrically a unit hypersphere. Hence, we treat similarity and alignment interchangeably. Additionally, we assume $f(\cdot)$ and $g(\cdot)$ vectors are L2-normalized, leading to $\text{sim}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \cos(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{v}$.

5.1.2.2 Supervised Contrastive Loss

For a batch of N randomly sampled anchor, positive, and label triples, $B = \{(x_i, x_i^+, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, the supervised contrastive loss (Khosla, et al., 2020), for each i -th triplet (x_i, x_i^+, y_i) is defined as:

$$l_i^{sup} = - \sum_{j \in P_i} \frac{1}{|P_i|} \log \frac{e^{z_i \cdot z_j^+ / \tau}}{\sum_{k=1}^N e^{z_i \cdot z_k^+ / \tau}}$$

Where $P_i = \{j | y_i = y_j\}$ is the set of indexes of all the samples with the same label as the i -th sample in the batch, and τ is the softmax temperature parameter that controls how soft/strongly positive pairs are pulled together and negative pairs pushed apart in the embedding space. The lower τ , the sharper the softmax output distribution and the stronger the push/pull factor. The final loss is computed across all the N pairs in the mini-batch as $\mathcal{L}^{sup} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N l_i^{sup}$.

5.1.2.3 Supervised Soft Contrastive Loss

Let $\delta(y_i, y_j)$ be a semantic similarity measure between labels y_i and y_j . We define our soft contrastive loss as follows:

$$l_i^{soft} = - \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{e^{\delta(y_i, y_j) / \tau}}{\sum_{k=1}^N e^{\delta(y_i, y_k) / \tau'}} \log \frac{e^{z_i \cdot z_j^+ / \tau}}{\sum_{k=1}^N e^{z_i \cdot z_k^+ / \tau}} \quad (2)$$

Where τ' is a temperature parameter controlling the "softness" of the negative labels. Unlike the supervised contrastive loss (Equation 1), this loss encourages the encoder to separate anchors and negatives proportionally to the semantic similarity of their labels. Finally, the mini-batch loss \mathcal{L}^{soft} is computed as in \mathcal{L}^{sup} .

5.1.2.4 Training targets

We experiment with four types of training targets, distinguished by whether the dialogue action label is used directly or decomposed into dialogue act and slot labels, and by the type of contrastive loss employed. Specifically, we consider the following two targets using the proposed soft contrastive loss:

- D2F_{single}: $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{act+slots}^{soft}$
- D2F_{joint}: $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{act}^{soft} + \mathcal{L}_{slots}^{soft}$

And the two corresponding targets using the default supervised contrastive loss:

- D2F-Hard_{single}: $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{act+slots}^{sup}$
- D2F-Hard_{joint}: $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{act}^{sup} + \mathcal{L}_{slots}^{sup}$

The subscript indicates the type of label used to compute the loss, either the dialogue action as a single label (act+slots)¹¹, or the dialogue act and slots separately. In the case of the joint loss, separate contrastive heads $g(\cdot)$ are employed.

5.1.3 TOD Dataset Construction and Evaluation Framework

One of the main bottlenecks in TOD systems' development and evaluation is the lack of a robust, standardized dataset that captures the full range of nuances present in real-world conversations. Accordingly, as part of our contribution, we constructed a large, standardized TOD dataset. For this, we identified and collected 20 TOD datasets from which we could extract dialog act and/or slot annotations.

We then manually inspected each dataset to locate and extract the necessary annotations, manually standardizing domain names and dialog act labels across datasets. Finally, we unified all datasets under a consistent format, incorporating per-turn dialog act and slot annotations. The resulting unified TOD dataset comprises 3.4 million utterances annotated with 18 standardized dialog acts, 524 unique slot labels, and 3,982 unique action labels (dialog act + slots) spanning across 52 different domains. This dataset is publicly available in HuggingFace.¹² Overall, our unified TOD dataset serves as a valuable resource for training and evaluating task-oriented dialog embeddings, offering a comprehensive and standardized collection of annotated interactions across diverse domains.

5.1.4 Evaluation framework

To assess the quality of the representation space geometry through the similarity of the embeddings representing different *actions* we use the following methods as quality proxies:

1. **Anisotropy:** we measured the anisotropy of a set of embeddings as the average cosine (absolute) similarity among all embeddings in the set. Ideally, embeddings of the same *action* should be similar (high intra-action anisotropy) while being dissimilar to those of other actions (low inter-action anisotropy). We report the average intra- and inter-action anisotropy across all actions.
2. **Similarity-based few-shot classification.** For this we use Prototypical Networks (Snell, Swersky, & Zemel, 2017) to perform a similarity-based classification. A prototype embedding for each *action* is calculated by averaging k of its embeddings (k -shot). All other embeddings are then classified based on the closest prototype embedding. We report the macro averaged F1 score and Accuracy for $k=1$ and $k=5$ (i.e., 1-shot and 5-shot classification).
3. **Ranking.** For each action, we randomly select one utterance as the query and retrieve the top- k closest embeddings, creating a ranking with their actions. Ideally, the top- k retrieved embeddings should predominantly correspond to the same *action* as the query, thus ranked first. We report Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (nDCG@10), averaged over all actions.

5.1.4.1 Baselines

As baseline approaches, we use two broad categories of different embedding types:

- **General Sentence Embeddings:**
 - GloVe: the average of GloVe embeddings (Pennington, Socher, & Manning, 2014)
 - BERT: the vanilla BERTbase model with mean pooling strategy, corresponding to our untrained encoder.
 - Sentence-BERT: the model with the best average performance reported among all Sentence-BERT pre-trained models, namely the all-mpnet-base-v2 model pre-trained using MPNet (Song, Tan, Qin, Lu, & Liu, 2020) and further fine-tuned on a 1 billion sentence pairs dataset.

¹¹ Dialogue acts represent the functional intent behind an utterance (e.g., *request, inform, confirm*), while slots are structured variables that capture specific information within that utterance (e.g., *location, time, symptom*).

¹² <https://huggingface.co/datasets/sergioburdisso/dialog2flow-dataset>

- GTR-T5: the Generalizable T5-based dense Retriever (Ni, et al., 2022) pre-trained on a 2 billion web question-answer pairs dataset, outperforming previous sparse and dense retrievers on the BEIR benchmark (Thakur, 2021).
- OpenAI: the recently released OpenAI’s text-embedding-3-large model (OpenAI, et al., 2024; Neelakantan, et al., 2022).
- **Dialog Sentence Embeddings:**
 - TOD-BERT: the TOD-BERT-jnt model reported in (Wu, Hoi, Socher, & Xiong, 2020) pre-trained to optimize a contrastive response selection objective by treating utterances and their dialog context as positive pairs.
 - DSE: pre-trained on the same dataset as TOD-BERT, DSE learns sentence embeddings by simply taking consecutive utterances of the same dialog as positive pairs for contrastive learning.
 - SBD-BERT: the TOD-BERT-SBDM WOZ model reported in (Qiu, Wu, Liu, & Xiong., 2022) in which sentences are represented as the mean pooling of the tokens that are part of the slots of the utterance, as identified by a Slot Boundary Detection (SBD) model trained on the original MultiWOZ dataset (Budzianowski, et al., 2018).
 - DialogGPT: following TOD-BERT and DSE, we also report results with DialogGPT (Zhang, et al., 2020) using the mean pooling of its hidden states as the sentence representation.
 - SPACE-2: a dialog representation model pre-trained on a corpus of 22.8 million utterances, 3.3 million of which are annotated with TOD labels (He, et al., 2022).

5.1.5 Experimental Results

Experiments were performed on a subset of our unified TOD dataset. Additional results on SpokenWOZ (Si, et al., 2023), the first large-scale human-to-human speech-text dataset for TOD are also described in (Burdisso, Madikeri, & Motlicek, 2024).

Figure 5-1 shows the experimental results for the similarity-based classification. Figure 5-2 shows the anisotropy results. Finally, Figure 5-3 summarizes the ranking-based results. Overall, our experimental results showed that all D2F variants consistently outperform the baselines across all metrics. This is expected, as D2F models, unlike the baselines, are explicitly trained to learn a representation space where embeddings are clustered by their corresponding actions. However, the baseline results serve as a proxy for assessing the inherent suitability of existing sentence embedding models for our objective.

Figure 5-1: Similarity-based few-shot classification results on our unified TOD evaluation set

Figure 5-2: Difference (deltas) between the intra- and inter-action anisotropy values, the higher the better

Figure 5-3: Ranking-based results on the unified TOD dataset. The higher the value the better the performance

5.1.5.1 Dialog flow extraction

One advantage of the D2F model is that it allows us to identify dialogue trajectories by means of modelling the problem of dialogue flow identification as the construction of a weighted action transition graph. In order to fully understand how the process of dialog flow extraction was implemented, please refer to (Burdizzo, Madikeri, & Motliceck, 2024). See Figure 5-4 as an example of a fully automatic flow identified from the “hospital” domain. This graph allows us to understand the common flow of the conversations with a degree of detail: first, the user and system greet each other (**U0** and **S6**), then the user inform the reason of the call requesting the phone number of a department (**U4**), the agent may confirm the department (**S7**) or request more information (**S4**) before providing the phone number (**S2**). The user may then either confirm the number (**U3**) or thank the system (**U5**). Finally, the system asks if anything else is required (**S5**), to which the user may either finish the conversation (**U6**) or, more likely, thank the system (**U2**) before the system says goodbye (**S0**).

5.1.6 Summary and Future Work Directions

The Dialog2Flow framework introduces a method for automatically extracting structured dialogue flows from unannotated conversations using action-driven sentence embeddings. By training models to represent utterances based on their underlying dialogue acts and slots, Dialog2Flow enables the recovery of implicit conversational structures critical for understanding and controlling complex dialogues. This approach is especially relevant in high-risk settings, where system responses must follow interpretable, verifiable interaction patterns.

Figure 5-4: Graph obtained from the hospital domain using the D2F model. Node labels correspond to their cluster ID along a representative utterance

The extracted flows can serve both as training data for supervised dialogue policy models and as evaluation scaffolds for assessing the faithfulness and coherence of LLM-generated dialogues. This connects directly to the methodology described in Section 3.1, where the goal is to ground LLM-based dialogue systems in task schemas or dialogue flows, thereby improving controllability, interpretability, and trustworthiness in domains where misalignment or hallucination can have critical consequences. Dialog2Flow contributes to this vision by offering a scalable and partially automated way of generating these dialogue structures from raw conversational data, including both audio and textual inputs.

Future work will focus on leveraging the extracted dialogue flows to guide and constrain LLM-based dialogue generation, improving controllability and reducing hallucinations. Additionally, we plan to explore flow-based evaluation metrics and extend the methodology to multimodal settings.

5.2 Context-Aware Dialogue with LLMs in High-Risk Domains: Insights from the NurseLLM Use Case

This chapter introduces the initial experimental baselines for building effective context-aware dialogue systems, using the NurseLLM as a case study. The NurseLLM, part of Pilot 4 (Upgrading support call centers through AI-based Supervision of multimodal dialogues) is designed to support medical staff by assisting in conversations with parents reporting health concerns about their newborns, with a strong emphasis on safety, factual consistency, and explainability. The focus lies on exploring how contextual integration—through static to dynamic techniques—can enhance LLM-based dialogue systems in high-risk, domain-specific scenarios.

Previously, in Section 3.2, we introduced two key types of contextual information—**static** and **dynamic**—that can be supplied to an LLM-based dialogue system to enable more efficient, natural, and coherent interactions. Thus, for the purpose of our research, a dialogue system is context-aware if it is provided with the information from both static and dynamic context and if it uses that information to generate the most appropriate next utterance in a dialogue with the caller. In this section, we describe the methods we plan on experimenting with to generate and provide context to the *NurseLLM*. An overview of our methodology is given in Figure 5-5.

Figure 5-5: Overview of our methodology for development of a context-aware dialogue system in the healthcare domain

5.2.1 Static context

5.2.1.1 Role, goal and guardrails: System prompt

The role, goal and guardrails of the *NurseLLM* will be set using prompt engineering. Prompt engineering plays an important role in ensuring that dialogue systems behave predictably and safely by providing clear, structured instructions that guide model behavior. In the context of medical dialogue systems, creating prompts with role definitions, such as “You are a nurse whose only task is to collect symptom information”, and specifying strict guardrails (e.g., “Do not provide medical advice,” “Only ask questions relevant to your role”) helps prevent unintended or harmful outputs (Bertalan, 2023), see for example an excerpt of the provided prompt to *NurseLLM* in Table 5-1. Guardrails transform open-ended LLM responses into focused dialogues, reducing hallucinations and scope creep by steering the model toward desired content and away from prohibited areas (Dong, et al., 2024). Systems like Google’s Articulate Medical Intelligence Explorer (Tu, et al., 2024) and Chat Ella (Zhang & Song, 2024) demonstrate how optimized prompts can support diagnostic reasoning conversations while maintaining clinician oversight. Commercial healthcare chatbots like Ada Health and Babylon Health rely on pre-defined prompts and disclaimers to gather patient data safely without overstepping into diagnostic advice (Zawati & Lang, 2024).

Table 5-1: Example excerpt of our system prompt aimed at role and goal guardrails

You are an AI assistant for a medical call center, helping with the *initial intake* of callers—mostly new parents seeking help with their newborns. Your job is to **efficiently gather all relevant information**, so that when a doctor becomes available, they can seamlessly take over the call with everything they need at hand

5.2.1.2 Role, goal and guardrails: Few-shot examples

Few-shot prompting means presenting the LLM with a small number of demonstration pairs—typically two to five—that exemplify the task’s structure, tone, and constraints. In contrast to zero-shot prompts (no examples) or extensive fine-tuning (many labeled instances), few-shot is pragmatic middle ground in accessing in-context learning capabilities of models like GPT-4 (Min, et al., 2022; OpenAI, et al., 2024). Studies in symptom classification or question answering have shown that few-shot prompting can raise accuracy by up to 5–10% over zero-shot baselines (Ge, Guo, Das, Al-Garadi, & Sarker, 2023).

When designing the *NurseLLM*, we plan to use few-shot examples to demonstrate:

- **Symptom Inquiry Structure** that will show the *NurseLLM* how to elicit symptoms and other relevant information in concise question–answer pairs.
- **Guardrail Compliance** that will illustrate refusal templates to the *NurseLLM* in cases when a user requests medical advice, e.g., “I’m not a licensed professional; please consult a doctor” rather than attempting a diagnosis.
- **Relevance Filtering** that will highlight how the *NurseLLM* should steer away from off-topic queries.

As a first step in our approach we plan to analyze relevant literature such as (Shi, et al., 2024) as well as similar systems such as Med-Flamingo (Moor, et al., 2023). Based on our findings we will create a set of initial few-shot examples which we will then iteratively refine.

5.2.1.3 Context-tracking instructions

In line with the previous section, we plan on designing specialized few-shot examples of different ways of context-tracking. One such example is given in Table 5-2.

Table 5-2: Example of a context-tracking instructional prompt for Context Retention

Always remember and refer back to symptoms or facts mentioned earlier in the conversation, even if the caller does not repeat them. Use previous information to ensure continuity and relevance in your follow-up questions.

Example 1:

CALLER: My baby has been vomiting and seems very tired.

NurseLLM: How long has your baby been vomiting?

CALLER: Since last night.

NurseLLM: Has your baby had any fever along with the vomiting and tiredness?

CALLER: No fever, just very sleepy.

NurseLLM: Thank you. Besides vomiting and sleepiness, have you noticed any other symptoms,...

5.2.2 Dynamic context

5.2.2.1 Previous Dialogue history

The role of the previous dialogue history is to enable the LLM to keep track of what's already been said in the dialogue so far. In our approach we plan to directly provide the *NurseLLM* with the full dialogue from the first up to the latest utterance by the caller (see Table 5-3).

Table 5-3: Example of previous dialogue history

CALLER: Good afternoon, can you hear me?

NurseLLM: Yes, yes, I can hear you, go ahead.

CALLER: Uh, good day, um, I'm calling about a baby who has had a fever for a few days.

NurseLLM: Okay, tell me how old the baby is.

CALLER: The baby is thirteen months old.

NurseLLM: Okay, and what was the highest temperature, how high did it go?

CALLER: Well, it went up mostly to thirty-eight point three, maybe thirty-eight point five, we're not entirely sure.

5.2.2.2 Named entities

To add an additional semantic layer of information on top of the full dialogue history, we plan on experimenting with providing the *NurseLLM* with named entities relevant for the symptom-collection task. Named entity recognition (NER) is fundamental for structuring and understanding medical dialogues. Chen et al. highlight that clinical conversations are rich in predefined medical entities and that extracting these entities is a basic first step for interpreting dialogue semantics (Xing, Yin, Yan, & Wang, 2021). Varshney et al. use NER to ground dialogue in knowledge by combining standard Unified Medical Language System (UMLS) concepts with entities predicted from conversations, building an augmented knowledge graph that improves chatbot responses (Varshney, Zafar, Behera, & Ekbal, 2023). Similarly, Qu et al. (2023) develop CMed-GPT, a model that incorporates entity and lexical embeddings during fine-tuning to boost biomedical dialogue understanding (Qu, Li, Ma, & Li, 2023). The authors in (Xing, Yin, Yan, & Wang, 2021) introduce a multi-turn dialogue LLM with a critical information distillation mechanism, significantly improving medical entity recognition and response quality in experiments on clinical conversations. These studies collectively show that focusing on entity extraction directly enhances the semantic understanding and effectiveness of dialogue systems.

Annotation procedure

Following the well-established methodology for annotation of medical entities (Pustejovsky & Stubbs, 2012) as a first step we selected an appropriate dataset of dialogues (described in detail in Section 5.3.1) and designed an annotation scheme defining the types of entities that will be annotated (Table A8-1 in the Appendix). The scheme was created in collaboration with nurses and computer science experts involved in creating and curating the dataset. We then created and refined the annotation guidelines to include examples of good and bad annotations as well as conflict resolution strategies. Using the guidelines and the scheme, we created an instruction prompt and use ChatGPT (OpenAI, et al., 2024) to provide initial annotations for the whole dataset. The initial annotation will then be manually checked and corrected in the next phase of the annotation process. During this phase 10% of our dataset will be annotated in parallel by multiple annotators and subsequently we will calculate inter-annotator agreement metrics such as *Krippendorff's alpha* (Krippendorff, 2013) and F_1 -based overlap. Table 5-4 illustrates an example fully annotated with NEs.

Thus, in order to accomplish our goal of adding an extra layer of semantics to *NurseLLM*, we will design a prompt that will include the annotation scheme, guidelines, conflict resolution strategies and examples. That prompt will be used to instruct a separate *TaggerLLM* that will automatically tag the named entities in the dialogue utterances.

We plan on experimenting with a range of open weights LLMs for this purpose. The extracted entities will be incorporated into the prompt instructing the *NurseLLM* to focus on them. An example of such a prompt is given in Table 5-4

Table 5-4: NurseLLM-Caller dialogue with Named Entity spans in bold font

<p>CALLER: "Good afternoon, can you hear me?"</p> <p><i>NurseLLM</i>: "Yes, yes, I can hear you, go ahead."</p> <p>CALLER: "Uh, good day, um, I'm calling about a baby who has had a [fever SYMPTOM] [for a few days DURATION]."</p> <p><i>NurseLLM</i>: "Okay, tell me [how old AGE] the baby is."</p> <p>CALLER: "The baby is [thirteen months old AGE]."</p> <p><i>NurseLLM</i>: "Okay, and what was the [highest DEGREE] [temperature SYMPTOM], how high did it go?"</p> <p>CALLER: "Well, it went up mostly to [thirty-eight point three QUANTITY], maybe [thirty-eight point five QUANTITY], we're [not entirely sure UNCERTAINTY]."</p> <p><i>NurseLLM</i>: "Okay, and [how many days DURATION] has the [temperature SYMPTOM] been [elevated DEGREE]?"</p> <p>CALLER: "Since [the day before yesterday TIME]."</p> <p><i>NurseLLM</i>: "Okay. And where did you [measure the temperature TEST]?"</p> <p>CALLER: "Well – we almost always [measured TEST] on the [forehead BODY_PART]. We used, now I don't know if that's important, we used that [digital thermometer MEDICAL_DEVICE]."</p> <p><i>NurseLLM</i>: "Okay, have you tried [measuring the temperature TEST] with [another thermometer MEDICAL_DEVICE], or in another place, for example, on the [armpit BODY_PART], in the [mouth BODY_PART], or [rectally BODY_PART]?"</p>
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Table 5-5: Example of an instructional prompt with named entities

<p>Focus your responses on the named entities extracted from the dialogue. Use these entities to guide your follow-up questions and ensure all relevant information is collected.</p> <p>Example 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <p>CALLER: My baby has been vomiting and seems very tired.</p> <p>Named Entities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SYMPTOM: vomiting - BEHAVIOR: very tired <p>NURSE: How long has your baby been vomiting?</p> <p>CALLER: Since last night.</p> <p>Named Entities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TIME: since last night

5.2.2.3 Retrieval-augmented few-shot example generation

We introduce a retrieval-augmented approach where the *NurseLLM* engages with parents of newborns by choosing contextually appropriate questions from an external repository. Our methodology comprises four stages. First, we plan to prepare our source materials which include: (1) a corpus of nurse–parent dialogues transcribed from telephone calls and (2) a collection of infant health question–answer pairs described in detail in Section 5.3.1. We then plan to annotate all the utterances in the dialogues and Q&A pairs with named entities using the *TaggerLLM* described in the previous section. The recognized entities will support filtering and ranking in the next stages. Next, we will embed each utterance into a semantic vector using a pre-trained embedding model. We plan on experimenting both with general domain and specialized embedding models. These embeddings will be stored in a vector store with efficient approximate nearest neighbor index. In the third stage, for the current utterance of the caller we will retrieve the *top-k* (e.g., $k = 10$) most similar questions from the vector store. We will filter retrieved candidates using lightweight rule-based checks based on the named entities tagged in the caller utterance (e.g., “fever,” “feeding difficulty”) to eliminate irrelevant candidates. To maximize informational diversity and avoid redundancy, we will apply a re-ranking algorithm such as maximal marginal relevance (MMR) (Carbonell & Goldstein, 1998), ensuring our final selection covers distinct facets of the caller’s concern.

5.2.3 Chain-of-Thought reasoning instructions

Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting was first formalized by (Wei, et al., 2022) who showed that instructing large language models (LLMs) to “think step by step” improves performance on multi-step reasoning tasks across arithmetic, commonsense, and symbolic manipulation benchmarks (Shi, et al., 2024). Follow-up work introduced self-consistency, aggregating multiple sampled reasoning paths to further stabilize and enhance accuracy (Singhal, et al., 2025). Liévin et al. demonstrated that CoT prompting improves performance of both closed source and open models in medical question answering (Xing, Yin, Yan, & Wang, 2021). Similar results were exhibited by Google’s Med-PaLM, enhanced with CoT-style instruction tuning (Singhal, et al., 2025), while Nachane et al. specialized clinical CoT prompts outperform standard five-shot CoT baselines in mirroring real-life differential diagnosis steps (Nachane, et al., 2024).

Thus, as an additional method for boosting the performance of the *NurseLLM* we plan on experimenting with chain-of-thought (CoT) reasoning instructions. Depending on the LLM we plan to enable the built-in CoT option or design our custom-tailored CoT prompt such as the one given in Table 5-6.

Table 5-6: Example of Chain-of-Thought instructional prompt

Table 5-6

Your primary task is to collect as much relevant symptom information as possible from parents or caregivers. For each response, think step by step before asking your next question. First, identify the main symptoms or facts mentioned by the caller. Next, reason about what additional details (such as duration, severity, or related symptoms) are needed to fully understand the situation. Then, formulate your next question to maximize information collection. Do not provide medical advice or diagnosis. Only ask questions relevant and always use your reasoning process internally before generating your next response.

5.3 Next response generation using LLM

A dataset of medical cases dialogue is created and curated from UNS, a main activity being developed within WP5. The dialogues of the dataset are both in Serbian and English. The dataset comprises 150 multi-turn medical dialogues of interaction between the nurse and the parent of the baby patient. Different models are examined in different prompt settings of each language version of the dataset. For the Serbian version of the dataset, there is a need of multilingual LLMs trained to be able to interact in Serbian language.

There are not many multilingual LLMs that support also Serbian, so we chose two multilingual LLMs that support a lot of European languages, which are EuroLLM and Salamandra. Specifically, EuroLLM (Martins P. H., et al., 2025) supports all European Union languages and 11 other languages such as Arabic, Catalan, Chinese, Galician, Hindi,

Japanese, Korean, Norwegian, Russian, Turkish, and Ukrainian. Salamandra (Gonzalez-Agirre, et al., 2025) supports more than 35 European languages (Serbian included) and some variants of them.

The *NurseLLM* model serves as the core component for managing dialogues and interacting with the caller. Given a conversational context, it generates the next response (i.e., utterance or turn). Thus, our task is framed as next response generation. The input to the model consists of both static and dynamic context (e.g., system prompt, dialogue history, current utterance), as defined in Section 3.2.1. This input is provided to the *NurseLLM*. The output of the model is the generated subsequent response. See an example of input and output in Table 5-7. We will evaluate the proposed methods using the datasets described in Section 5.3.1. Results will be evaluated using both standard and custom metrics. Standard metrics include common automatic metrics such as BLEU (Papineni, Roukos, Ward, & Zhu, 2002) and ROUGE (Lin, 2004), which assess the similarity between generated and reference responses. Custom metrics are tailored for the context-aware medical dialogue setting, such as entity coverage, context retention, and asking relevant questions, as detailed in Section 5.2. For our baseline experiments, we use two prompting strategies and two state-of-the-art (SOTA) LLMs.

Table 5-7: Example of model input and output. The input consists of a system prompt and previous dialogue turns, while the output is the subsequent response generated by NurseLLM. The system prompt shown here is truncated for clarity

<p>Input</p> <p>You are an AI assistant for a medical...</p> <p><i>Caller:</i> Good afternoon, can you hear me?</p> <p><i>NurseLLM:</i> Yes, yes, I can hear you, go ahead.</p> <p><i>Caller:</i> Uh, good day, um, I'm calling about a baby who has had a fever for a few days.</p> <p><i>NurseLLM:</i> Okay, tell me how old the baby is.</p> <p><i>Caller:</i> The baby is thirteen months old.</p> <hr/> <p>Output</p> <p><i>NurseLLM:</i> Okay, and what was the highest temperature, how high did it go?</p>
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5.3.1 Datasets

5.3.1.1 UNS dataset

The UNS dataset is a new corpus of medical dialogues designed to simulate realistic interactions in a healthcare call center. Each dialogue revolves around infant health topics and is conducted in Serbian. To create this dataset, nurses and callers participated in recorded conversations where the discussion topic was pre-arranged. Rather than following a rigid script, the dialogues were guided loosely to promote natural and authentic exchanges. After recording, the dialogues were transcribed and manually refined for accuracy. To broaden experimentation, the transcriptions were translated to English, enhanced through prompting using an LLM, and then manually refined by experts. The resulting dataset consists of 150 high-quality, multi-turn dialogues available in both Serbian and English. An example dialogue excerpt is shown in Table 5-3.

This dataset is uniquely suited for our work, as it features context-aware and multi-turn dialogues simulating conversations from a medical call center with a focus on collecting information and symptoms from the caller. This is precisely the environment our models are designed to operate in. To the best of our knowledge, no existing publicly available dataset meets this combination of criteria. As such, this dataset is crucial for both training and evaluating models in this domain.

5.3.1.2 Datasets for retrieval-augmented approach

In addition to the UNS dataset, we plan to use two datasets for our retrieval-augmented few-shot example generation approach, as described in Section 5.2.2.3. The first dataset consists of question-answer (Q&A) pairs

related to infant health topics in Serbian. These pairs cover domains such as nursing, infant health, and early childhood development. The source data was written by trained medical professionals and subsequently transformed into QA format using a state-of-the-art commercial LLM. The prompt used for generation is shown in Table 5-8. This dataset serves as a source for retrieving semantically relevant examples in Serbian. We provide English translation for illustration, but the original prompt was in Serbian to ensure linguistic and contextual fidelity.

The second dataset is *NoteChat* (Wang, et al., 2024), a large-scale collection of over 207,000 patient-physician conversations in English. Each conversation averages multiple turns, closely matching the structure of our UNS dataset. Dialogues were synthetically generated by LLMs by conditioning on real-world clinical notes. This resulted in multi-turn, context-aware dialogues that align well with our focus on symptom collection and context tracking. While the UNS dataset is focused on infant-related questions, *NoteChat* spans a broad range of medical domains, so only a subset is directly relevant to our use case. Nevertheless, *NoteChat* remains a useful resource for retrieval-augmented approach in our context.

Table 5-8: Prompt for generating question-answer pairs from medical texts in Serbian

Transform the following text into a Q&A format. The key rules are:

1. Questions and answers must be derived exclusively from the given text.
2. It is forbidden to add information that is not present in the text.
3. Each question must be formulated in a single sentence.
4. Each answer can have a maximum of two sentences.
5. All questions and answers must be in Serbian.
6. Each question-answer pair must be separated by blocks with #!#.
7. An individual question starts with "Question: ", followed by the question text, and ends with the marker #!
8. An individual answer starts with "Answer: ", followed by the answer text, and ends with the marker #!

Example:

#!#

...

#!#

Question: {question text} #!

Answer: {answer text} #!

#!#

...

#!#

Here is the text:...

5.3.2 Evaluation metrics

We evaluated generated responses using standard automatic (objective) metrics to assess model performance. We plan on expanding evaluation with domain-specific (subjective) metrics in future experiments.

5.3.2.1 Automatic metrics

We applied BLEU and ROUGE scores to quantify n-gram overlap between generated and reference responses. BLEU measures the precision of n-grams in the generated text compared to the reference, providing an indication of how closely the model output matches the expected response. ROUGE focuses on recall and is commonly used to

evaluate the quality of summaries and generated text by comparing overlapping units such as n-grams, word sequences, and word pairs. Additionally, we used BERTScore (Zhang, Kishore, Wu, Weinberger, & Artzi, 2019), which leverages contextual embeddings from pre-trained language models to compute semantic similarity between generated and reference responses. BERTScore is particularly useful for capturing meaning beyond surface-level n-gram overlap, making it well-suited for evaluating the nuanced and context-sensitive nature of medical dialogues.

These metrics provide a common, standardized, and objective basis for evaluating next response generation (Radford, et al., 2019) (Wang, et al., 2024) (Arias-Duart, et al., 2025) (Fraile Navarro, et al., 2025). They are particularly useful in our setting due to their widespread adoption and ease of use. While useful, they often fail to capture critical details in multi-turn dialogues (Zheng, et al., 2023). Therefore, we will introduce custom domain-specific metrics to address these limitations.

5.3.2.2 Domain-specific metrics

To address the limitations of standard automatic metrics, we will introduce custom domain-specific metrics. We will adopt the *LLM-as-a-judge* paradigm (Zheng, et al., 2023), where a dedicated evaluation LLM is used to evaluate the model's output according to predefined instructions. Following this paradigm, we plan to utilize a dedicated LLM, called *EvalLLM*, to evaluate the outputs of *NurseLLM*. For instance, *NurseLLM* should not provide direct medical advice (described in Section 5.2), and *EvalLLM* will be tasked to verify that guideline. In addition, *EvalLLM* will evaluate adherence to other critical instructions, such as context retention, contextual inference, handling implicit information, and resolving contextual inconsistency (described in Section 5.2.1). Finally, *EvalLLM* will be tasked with evaluating whether all relevant symptoms have been collected. Specifically, it will compare the set of symptoms from the dialogue by *NurseLLM* with the ground truth set of named entities extracted by *TaggerLLM* (Section 5.2.2.2). In this way, *EvalLLM* will enable a comprehensive, systematic, and consistent evaluation of model behavior with respect to clinical safety, context awareness, and task requirements.

5.3.3 Baseline experimental setup

Our main goal is to develop approaches for improving context-aware dialogue systems. Thus, we focus on developing and evaluating algorithms for context-aware dialogue systems defined in Section 5.2. To assess the quality of these algorithms, we designed baseline experiments, described in the rest of this section. As our model of choice for *NurseLLM*, we employed Gemma 3 (Team, et al., 2025) for the English version of the dataset and EuroLLM and Salamandra for the Serbian version of the dataset. All experiments were evaluated with automatic metrics (described in Section 5.3.2) and the ground truth next utterance responses of the English version and the Serbian version of the UNS dataset respectively.

5.3.3.1 Preparing the dataset

To prepare the data for the baseline experiments, we construct input-output pairs as follows: the input consists of the system prompt and the previous dialogue history, while the ground-truth (i.e., output) is the nurse's subsequent response (as in Table 5-4). We use this setup to compare generated responses by *NurseLLM* with the ground-truth responses from the dataset. Note that all conversation histories are drawn directly from the ground-truth transcripts to ensure evaluation consistency.

5.3.3.2 Setup 1 - System prompt variants

We first compare system prompts to identify the most effective one. For this experiment and for the English version of the dataset, we used the smaller Gemma 3 4B model as *NurseLLM* for efficiency, before scaling to larger variants and for the Serbian version we used Salamandra 7B and EuroLLM 9B. To accomplish this, we evaluated different system prompts with zero-shot prompting. We assessed three variants: a minimal prompt (baseline 0), an intermediate prompt with basic instructions (baseline 1), and a comprehensive prompt with detailed instructions (baseline 2). Once we established the best prompt, we utilized it for all subsequent experiments.

5.3.3.3 Setup 2 - Model size impact

We examine the impact of model capacity on performance across different parameter sizes ranging from 4B to 27B. Specifically, we conducted experiments with 4B, 12B, and 27B parameter versions of Gemma 3. We tested this in

the zero-shot setting with the best prompt variant. Once we established the best model size, we utilized that model for all subsequent experiments.

5.3.3.4 Setup 3 - Target language

Our dataset is available in both Serbian and English. This dual-language setup enables us to evaluate model performance in a high-resource language (English) and a lower-resource language (Serbian). We applied the optimal prompt and the best-performing model to both languages using the standard zero-shot setting. For Serbian, we used both the translated version of the prompt and the English original prompt with an added instruction to give the responses only in Serbian. This experiment provides insights into the ability of LLMs to reason and perform across languages within our specific domain.

5.3.3.5 Setup 4 – Zero-shot vs few-shot prompting

We compared zero-shot and few-shot prompting to assess the impact of including example dialogues. In the zero-shot approach, the model receives the best system prompt variant and a previous conversation history, as in the previous experiments. No example dialogues were provided in this setting. In the few-shot approach, the model receives a small number of example dialogues in addition to the system prompt and conversation history. These examples are selected to illustrate the desired conversational style, adherence to safety guidelines, and context tracking. This approach allows the model to better generalize to the specific requirements of medical dialogue generation. To perform this, we took two conversations from the UNS dataset and appended them to the system prompt. Thus, the input to the model is a system prompt, conversation examples, and previous conversation turns. Note that the few-shot examples were excluded from the evaluation set to ensure a fair comparison. Other conditions, such as model size and prompt variant, remained identical to the zero-shot approach.

5.3.3.6 Setup 5 – English vs Serbian prompting

We also compared the capability of the model to handle the static context, that is, the objective, the goal and the instructions part of prompting, when given in English and in Serbian. Open-source multilingual LLMs that are trained on many different languages are expected to behave well in different language input setup. Despite their multilingual capabilities, LLMs have been trained on bigger amount of English text than other languages. There are a lot more available text, corpus and data in English than in other languages and most pretrained LLMs are initially trained solely in English. Thus, we wanted to figure out if prompting in English is a better choice than Serbian. Both the English and the Serbian version of the dataset are included in the Appendix at Table A-8-2.

5.3.3.7 Setup 6 - LLMs

We set out to evaluate different LLMs as *NurseLLM* in the zero-shot setting. For this test, we compared our primary model, Gemma 3, with EuroLLM (Martins P. H., et al., 2024). Gemma 3 is a general-domain, state-of-the-art open-weight model that demonstrates strong performance across benchmarks in language understanding, generation, and instruction-following. Its open-weight nature enables transparent evaluation and reproducibility—crucial in sensitive domains like healthcare. It is lightweight enough to run on a single GPU, simplifying deployment. Gemma 3 was explicitly trained to enhance reasoning capabilities through reward-based fine-tuning, improving its ability to infer user intent, follow conversational guardrails, and maintain coherence across turns. These qualities make it particularly suitable for our context tracking instructions (see Section 5.2.1.3). In contrast, EuroLLM is a multilingual LLM designed to support over 24 EU languages. It is fully open-sourced, providing not only open weights but also access to its training code and data. Another open-source multilingual LLM is Salamandra which supports more than 35 European languages, including Serbian. Salamandra is built on a decoder-based transformer architecture and has been trained from scratch on trillion of tokens. The open approach aligns well with the reproducibility and transparency goals that are critical in domains like healthcare.

5.3.4 Baseline results

In this section, we present the results of our baseline experiments on the UNS dataset in Figure 55-6 and Figure 55-7. We first compared different system prompts to identify the most effective one. Next, we examined the impact of model capacity and identified the best-performing model. We then evaluated performance across languages by comparing results on both the Serbian and English versions of the UNS dataset. Additionally, we compared zero-shot and few-shot prompting to assess the benefits of including example dialogues. We also evaluated another

multilingual LLM in the zero-shot setting. Finally, we identified and discussed the limitations of standard automatic evaluation metrics.

Figure 55-6 Baseline experiments on the UNS dataset in English. Automatic evaluation metrics are reported.

As shown in Figure 55-6, the comprehensive prompt (baseline 2) outperformed the others across all metrics: BLEU improved from 0.0046 (baseline 0) to 0.0127 (baseline 2), ROUGE-1 from 0.119 to 0.154, ROUGE-2 from 0.021 to 0.031, and BERTScore F1 from 0.646 to 0.685. These improvements are attributed to the explicit and detailed instructions in the comprehensive prompt. Based on these gains, we adopt the comprehensive prompt (baseline 2) for all subsequent experiments. Each bar corresponds to a specific experiment, with names in the format: model @ prompt @ language. For example, gemma-3-4b-it @ system - baseline 2 @ eng refers to the Gemma 3 4B model, using system prompt variant 'baseline 2', evaluated on English data. System prompt variants are labeled as 'baseline 0', 'baseline 1', and 'baseline 2'. The experiments include different prompt variants, model sizes, and prompting methods (zero-shot and few-shot). The few-shot setting with Gemma 3 27B achieves the highest scores across all metrics.

5.3.4.1 Model size impact

We conducted this experiment with the 4B, 12B, and 27B parameter versions of Gemma 3, all using the baseline 2 prompt (Figure 55-6). As expected, larger models generally performed better. Moving from Gemma 3 4B (BERTScore F1 0.685) to Gemma 3 12B (BERTScore F1 0.699) resulted in a noticeable improvement. The increase from Gemma 3 12B to Gemma 3 27B (BERTScore F1 0.701) provided a further, albeit smaller, gain. These results indicate that larger models are better at capturing richer semantic details and improving response quality.

Figure 55-7 Comparison of zero-shot performance of Gemma 3 27B on the UNS dataset in English and Serbian.

5.3.4.2 Target language

The results are reported in Figure 55-7. While the scores on English data were higher for BERTScore F1 (0.701 compared to 0.684), the Serbian evaluation yielded slightly higher results for BLEU and ROUGE. This indicates that, although Gemma 3 was trained mostly on English data, it generalizes well to low-resource languages such as Serbian, achieving competitive results (Team, et al., 2025).

5.3.4.3 English VS Serbian prompting

Considering that EuroLLM has not been explicitly trained in Serbian and that even multilingual LLMs have been trained with a lot more English text than other languages, it was desired to compare how the two open-sourced LLMs behave when they are given the prompt in English and in Serbian. Having a look at Figure 5-8, we can see that Salamandra was able to perform better when the prompt was given in English. On the other hand, for the case of EuroLLM there was no actual impact on the result.

5.3.4.4 Zero-shot vs few-shot prompting

In addition to the zero-shot setting, we evaluated the few-shot prompting approach, which achieved the highest scores across all metrics (Figure 55-6). For instance, BERTScore F1 increased from 0.701 to 0.739. This demonstrates that enriching the prompt with relevant conversation examples can substantially improve model performance. These results further motivate our proposed prompting-based methods described in Section 5.2.1.1.

5.3.4.5 Gemma 3 vs EuroLLM & EuroLLM vs Salamandra

We compared the largest EuroLLM model with 9B parameters to Gemma 3 (Figure 55-6). EuroLLM achieved a BERTScore F1 of 0.707 in the zero-shot setting, slightly surpassing the 0.701 F1 of Gemma 3 27B under the same conditions. This outcome is likely due to the limitations of automatic metrics, which may not capture clinical relevance. Metrics such as BERTScore can emphasize surface similarity rather than task-specific performance. In the future, we plan to investigate this further with domain-specific evaluation, utilizing *EvaLLM* (Section 5.3.2.2).

Figure 5-8: Comparison of zero-shot performance of EuroLLM-9B and Salamandra-7B on the Serbian version of UNS dataset.

We also compared EuroLLM 9B parameters with Salamandra 7B parameters to see which open multilingual LLM behaves better. From Figure 5-8 we can see that all metrics, except for BLEU score, are higher when Salamandra is used as the NurseLLM. This was expected as EuroLLM is not explicitly trained on Serbian; it includes all European Union and some more languages, however Serbian is a Slavic language and EuroLLM has seen during training other Slavic-based languages such as Croatian which are closely related to Serbian.

5.3.4.6 Limitations of standard metrics

We note that standard metrics such as BLEU, ROUGE, and BERTScore quantify n-gram overlap and broad semantic similarity but are limited. They often miss critical details in medical dialogues, which cannot be identified using these measures. This is demonstrated in Table 5-9. In the first row, the model’s prediction is close to the ground truth, yet they ask about different symptoms; the model should have asked about the stomach, but it asked about fever—two clinically distinct symptoms. In the second row, the model’s prediction is correct and clinically equivalent to the ground truth, yet it receives a lower BERTScore than the first row. These examples were extracted from our baseline experiments on the Serbian UNS dataset and translated to English for illustration. The first example shows a clinically incorrect prediction with a high score, while the second example is clinically correct but receives a slightly lower score. This highlights the limitations of standard automatic metrics in evaluating medical dialogues. Reported examples demonstrate that BERTScore can be misleading. While BERTScore can capture semantic similarity, it does not reliably distinguish between clinically correct and incorrect responses. Such limitations motivate the development of *EvalLLM* and domain-specific evaluation metrics (Section 5.3.2.2).

Table 5-9: Comparison of reference and predicted responses with BERTScore.

Reference	Prediction	BERTScore
Okay, and have you perhaps noticed if the baby’s stomach is bloated?	Okay, I understand. Have you noticed if the baby has a fever?	0.796
Okay, and how old is the child?	I understand. How old is your child?	0.794

5.3.5 Summary and Future Directions

Our baseline experiments on the UNS dataset reveal several key insights into model performance across prompts, model capacities, languages, and evaluation setups. First, using a comprehensive system prompt (baseline 2) significantly improved automatic evaluation scores across all metrics, underscoring the importance of clear and informative prompting. Model capacity had a clear impact on quality: larger models (e.g., Gemma 3 27B) consistently outperformed smaller ones. Few-shot prompting further boosted performance, with BERTScore F1 increasing from 0.701 in the zero-shot setting to 0.739, confirming the benefit of providing dialogue examples. Multilingual evaluation showed that despite being predominantly trained on English, the models generalized well to Serbian, with only slight performance differences across languages. Interestingly, while Salamandra performed better with English prompts, EuroLLM showed consistent results across both Serbian and English, reflecting differences in multilingual training coverage. Comparisons between LLMs revealed that EuroLLM slightly outperformed Gemma 3 in zero-shot settings, and Salamandra generally surpassed EuroLLM on Serbian data—except for BLEU. Importantly, we observed limitations in standard evaluation metrics: BERTScore and ROUGE often failed to capture clinical correctness, motivating our development of EvalLLM for more accurate, domain-specific assessments.

Future work on next-response generation for context-aware dialogue systems—particularly in the NurseLLM use case—will focus on refining generation quality, grounding, and evaluation using a multi-pronged strategy. First, we plan to conduct few-shot experiments to test the system’s ability to generalize from limited examples. This will be paired with an evaluation pipeline (EvalLLM) where a reliable LLM will be used to assess generated responses based on criteria including avoiding medical advice, retaining context, and performing contextual inference. These automated evaluations will later be compared with human judgments to validate alignment and trustworthiness.

To improve generation quality and reduce hallucinations, we will incorporate a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) approach. This involves dynamically supplying the LLM with relevant, domain-specific examples to enhance contextual grounding. Two primary datasets will power this approach: (1) a curated set of Serbian Q&A pairs on infant health authored by medical professionals, and (2) the NoteChat dataset, which includes over 207k multi-turn English dialogues between patients and physicians, derived from real clinical notes.

6 Conclusions

The activities within WP3 contribute to the broader goals of ELOQUENCE by developing techniques that enhance the explainability and trustworthiness of AI-based conversational systems. These developments are intended to improve system behavior across both low-risk domains—such as smart home assistance—and high-risk environments, including healthcare support and service call supervision. Specifically, WP3 aligns with Pilot 1 (Privacy-preserving language model learning through decentralized training in smart homes) and Pilot 4 (AI-based supervision of multimodal dialogues to upgrade support call centers), focusing on strategies for making LLM-based dialogue agents more transparent, controllable. Efforts reported in this document span several complementary strategies. These include federated summarization and multi-turn dialogue memory construction, which help maintain consistency and contextual coherence. Additionally, the development of fine-grained relevance cues for information retrieval models boosts transparency in system decisions, while a novel span-copying mechanism supports more efficient and reliable text generation by reducing redundant computation—an especially valuable asset for real-time, low-latency applications.

A central conceptual contribution is the definition of contextual information and knowledge within the context of the planned activities (Chapter 3). For instance, the STAR dataset, proposes a methodology which suggests modeling dialogue as structured trajectories grounded in domain-specific knowledge. This approach addresses two core challenges in current LLM-based dialogue systems: hallucination and lack of controllability. STAR introduces mechanisms to inject task schemas and flow structures into the model’s decision-making process. This enables systems to better track conversational goals, adhere to predefined interaction flows, and generate responses that are explainable and aligned with user intent. STAR also supports the development of flow-based evaluation metrics, offering alternatives to traditional word-level scores like BLEU or ROUGE, and opening pathways for more meaningful assessments of system behavior.

Building on this foundation, ELOQUENCE’s proposed Dialog2Flow approach (Section 5.1) offers a methodology for extracting interpretable dialogue flows from unstructured dialogue data—either semi- or fully automatically. D2F converts dialogues into finite-state graphs representing typical conversational trajectories, thus bridging the gap between opaque LLM responses and structured domain expectations. Applied to real-world data, this methodology reveals whether conversations follow coherent patterns or deviate unpredictably, offering a powerful tool for both system evaluation and debugging. In the context of Pilot 4, D2F could potentially serve as a mechanism to audit AI-assistant interactions, ensuring adherence to customer support protocols and enhancing human oversight.

Finally, the *NurseLLM* use case (Sections 5.2 and 5.3) serves as an early experimental testbed for context-aware and explainable dialogue in a high-risk medical domain. The system supports medical staff by guiding conversations with parents reporting health concerns about their newborns. WP3’s role in this use case is to design mechanisms that ensure responses are contextually accurate, transparent, and grounded in reliable knowledge. These features are vital for fostering trust and mitigating the risks of miscommunication. *NurseLLM* also provides a practical avenue for applying earlier WP3 developments, such as multi-turn context integration, response traceability, and early dialogue flow analysis—bringing theoretical advances into direct alignment with real-world safety requirements.

Together, these activities illustrate how WP3 is laying the groundwork for explainable, controllable, and human-aligned AI dialogue systems. The current deliverable presents a coherent strategy supported by concrete baselines and early implementations. Looking ahead, WP3 will deepen these efforts by addressing key open questions: What forms of knowledge are most useful for grounding? When and how should this knowledge be injected into dialogue models? And what evaluation frameworks best reflect user-centered performance? A key milestone already achieved is a shared understanding among partners on the types of domain knowledge to be incorporated across tasks, ensuring consistency and scalability in the upcoming phases. These developments are instrumental to the ELOQUENCE vision—empowering dialogue systems to operate responsibly and effectively across both every day and highly-critical interactions.

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8 Appendix

8.1 Annotation scheme for Named Entities

Table A8-1: Annotation scheme for named entities in NurseLLM-Caller dialogues.

Entity Type	Description
ABNORMALITY	Open-ended inquiries (e.g., "anything unusual")
AGE	Child's age (e.g., "two months old", "how old")
BEHAVIOR	Observable action/change (e.g., "crying", "[refusing] milk", "sleepy", "[what about his] appetite")
BODY_PART	Specific body part (e.g., "eye", "stomach", "diaper area")
CAREGIVER_SUPPORT	Available support (e.g., "grandma helps")
CHARACTERISTIC	Adjectival qualities only (e.g., "yellowish," "thick," "reddened," "scaly," "cold to touch")
CHILD_TRAIT	Traits or behavioral tendencies (e.g., "active", "easy-going", "loves to nurse")
CHILD_MEDICAL_HISTORY	Chronic medical conditions or allergies relevant to the child's health (e.g., "asthma", "allergic to peanuts")
CLARIFICATION	Requests for clarity (e.g., "Do you mean...", "What exactly do you mean by...")
CLOTHES	Clothing or dress descriptors (e.g., "sleep suit", "mittens", "[lightly] clothed")
CONCERN	Expressed worry or doubt (e.g., "I'm worried," "I can't reach her")
DEGREE	Intensity or degree of a symptom (e.g., "mild", "very high")
DURATION	Time interval (e.g., "for two days", "since yesterday")
ENVIRONMENT	Physical setting (e.g., "dark room", "in the park", "room temperature")
FEEDING	All aspects of the baby's food and fluid intake, including method (e.g. "breastfeeding", "bottle feeding") and schedule (e.g. "before meals", "every three hours")
FOOD	Specific food items (e.g., "apple", "porridge", "cereal")
HYDRATION	Fluid intake (e.g., "lots of water", "coffee")
INTERVENTION	Caregiver health- or feeding-related actions (e.g., "aspirated manually", "warmed", "shook the bottle")
KINDERGARTEN	Daycare attendance (e.g., "in kindergarten", "not yet enrolled")
MEDICAL_DEVICE	Tools or devices (e.g., "digital thermometer", "nasal aspirator")

MOTHER_NUTRITION	Mother's diet or fluid intake (e.g., "ate fruit", "drank only coffee all day")
MOTHER_OTHER	Other mother issues (e.g., "postpartum bleeding", "infection")
OUTCOME	Reaction or result (e.g., "slept after", "burped", "[now she's] fine")
QUANTITY	Amounts, dosages, outputs of test (e.g., "thirty-eight point three", "two doses", "5 ml", "one sip")
SOCIAL_STRESS	Social stressors or emotional pressures on the caregiver (e.g., "home alone with 3 kids", "left by herself with the baby", "we're not sure if I can handle this", "recent argument in the family")
STOOL	Bowel movements or stool appearance (e.g., "runny stool", "five dirty diapers")
STORAGE_METHOD	Storage actions (e.g., "kept in fridge", "stored at room temperature")
SYMPTOM	Bodily signs, feelings, or excretions (e.g., "fever," "pain," "mucus," "discharge," "wet diaper")
TEST	Measurement or check (e.g., "checked the temperature", "tested milk flow")
TIME	Time reference (e.g., "yesterday", "a week ago", "3 hours before")
TREATMENT	Medications or remedies (e.g., "Tylenol", "saline solution")
EVENT	Preceding event or cause (e.g., "fell off the bed")
UNCERTAINTY	Doubt or approximation (e.g., "we think", "we're not sure")
URINATION	Urination events (e.g., "wet diaper", "no urine for 8 hours")
VACCINATION_STATUS	Immunization state (e.g., "up-to-date", "delayed")

8.2 Prompt Definition

Table A-8-2: The English and the Serbian version of zero-shot prompting.

English Prompt	Serbian Prompt
<p>####</p> <p># Instructions for the AI Chatbot in Medical Call Centers</p> <p>## Role and Purpose</p> <p>You are an AI assistant that supports medical call center staff in the initial communication with</p>	<p>####</p> <p># Uputstva za AI četbota u medicinskim kol centrima</p> <p>## Uloga i svrha</p> <p>Vi ste AI asistent koji pomaže osoblju medicinskog kol centra u početnoj komunikaciji</p>

callers—mainly new parents seeking advice about their newborns. You have the role of a NURSE (SESTRA) and you respond to what the CALLER (POZIVALAC) says. Your primary tasks are:

- Gathering relevant medical information from the caller.
- Transparently informing them of your AI nature.
 - You can not provide any medical advice.
 - Your responses should be concise.

Few Shot Examples

You should take into consideration the following few-shot examples to understand the context and format of the conversation.

{shots}

Final Note

Your goal is to simplify the call process and ensure that medical professionals receive clear and well-organized information. Keep communication clear and concise. All responses must be **EXCLUSIVELY** in Serbian. Do **NOT** return any answer in English. Return only the next utterance of the NURSE (SASTRE).

{conversation_history}

{user_query}

""

sa pozivaocima — uglavnom novim roditeljima koji traže savet u vezi sa svojim novorođenčecom. Vaša uloga je SESTRA, i odgovarate na ono što POZIVALAC kaže. Vaši glavni zadaci su:

- Prikupljanje relevantnih medicinskih informacija od pozivaoca.
- Transparentno informisanje da ste AI.
- Ne smete davati medicinske savete.
- Vaši odgovori treba da budu sažeti.

Few Shot Examples

Treba da uzmete u obzir sledeće primere sa nekoliko uputstava kako biste razumeli kontekst i format razgovora.

{shots}

Vaš cilj je da pojednostavite proces poziva i obezbedite da medicinski radnici dobiju jasne i dobro organizovane informacije. Držite komunikaciju jasnom i sažetom. Svi odgovori moraju biti **ISKLUČIVO** na srpskom jeziku. **NE** vraćajte nijedan odgovor na engleskom. Vratite samo sledeću repliku **MEDICINSKE SESTRE (SESTRE)**.

{conversation_history}

{user_query}

""

